

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D3.3

Critical ChangeLab Impact Evaluation

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Authors	Mairéad Hurley, Anne Pender, Shaun Ussher, Caitlin White (TCD), Lorelaj Lukačin, Boris Jokić (ISRZ)
Contributors	Critical ChangeLab Consortium
Reviewers	Iva Odak (ISRZ) Eva Durall Gazulla (UOULU)

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Glossary

CCLAB	Critical ChangeLab
Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ)	Questionnaire measuring democratic attitudes, practices, and perceptions
D	Deliverable
T	Task
WP	Work Package
MYCELIA	CCLAB mentorship programme for young activists and cultural practitioners, developed as part of Task 4.3
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
AI	Artificial Intelligence

Project Consortium

UOULU	University of Oulu (Finland)
TCD	Trinity College Dublin (Ireland)
UB	University of Barcelona (Spain)
WAAG	Waag Futurelab (Netherlands)
AE	Ars Electronica (Austria)
KERSNIKOVA	KERSNIKOVA (Slovenia)
TT	Tactical Tech (Netherlands)
ALTEREURO	European Alternatives (France)
ISRZ	Institute for Social Research in Zagreb (Croatia)
LAT	LATRA (Greece)

Executive Summary

This report, *Critical ChangeLab Impact Evaluation*, serves as Deliverable 3.3 of the Critical ChangeLab Project, presenting the findings of Task 3.2 within Work Package 3 (EVALUATE). The evaluation assesses the impact of the Critical ChangeLab (CCLAB) project on its three principal stakeholder groups: youth participants, educators, and consortium members.

The CCLAB project (2023–2026) is a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action involving ten partner institutions across Europe. It developed and implemented a flexible model of democratic pedagogy through three iterative cycles of Participatory Action Research (PAR), engaging over 2,100 young people and 290 educators across 19 European countries. The impact evaluation complements the process evaluation (D3.1: Malinverni et al., 2026), the final CCLAB Model for Democratic Pedagogy (D3.2: Durall et al., 2026), and the socioeconomic evaluation and policy recommendations (D3.4: Del Razo Martínez et al., 2026).

A mixed-methods evaluation design was adopted, combining quantitative survey data from 169 educators with qualitative data from semi-structured interviews with youth participants and with consortium member representatives, supplemented by PAR Cycle 3 evaluation records, and formative feedback on the CCLAB Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ). Data were analysed using a combined deductive and inductive thematic analysis approach.

After taking part in the CCLAB project activities, **youth participants** reported positive impacts on communication, critical thinking, and collaboration skills, as well as an increased sense of personal agency. Several moved from passive online engagement to active involvement in local and European-level democratic initiatives. **Educators** reported high levels of confidence in integrating democratic pedagogy into their future work, with those who had deeper engagement with the project through the PAR cycles consistently reporting stronger impacts. Respondents who had completed the CCLAB Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) '*Youth, democracy and technology - Participatory approaches for critical consciousness*', additionally reported meaningful shifts in how they understand the relationship between youth, democracy, and technology. **Consortium members** reported extensive impacts on partnerships and networks at institutional, community, national, and European levels, with all ten organisations identifying opportunities for future collaboration, and several partners embedding CCLAB approaches into their teacher education programmes, research agendas, and institutional strategies.

The findings were interpreted through a Three Orders of Change framework (Bartunek & Moch, 1987), adapted for the democratic education context. The evaluation identified substantial evidence of first-order change (impacts *about* democracy) and second-order change (impacts *for* democracy), with emerging evidence of third-order change (impacts *as* democracy) in the form of shifts in beliefs, values, and assumptions among participants and organisations. However, third-order change was not an explicit CCLAB project objective, and these impacts remained concentrated at the level of individual and organisational perspective shifts rather than systemic institutional transformation.

The evaluation acknowledges several limitations, most notably the smaller-than-anticipated youth interview sample. In addition, the distribution of youth impact assessment across the project's work packages shaped the scope of this deliverable. The most substantial body of youth data was gathered through the PAR cycles and analysed by Malinverni et al. (2026) in D3.1 'Critical ChangeLab process and recommendations for practice', while this deliverable was designed to draw on a complementary set of youth experiences. Readers seeking a comprehensive picture of the project's effects on youth are encouraged to read the findings in this report in conjunction with D3.1.

Recommendations are directed at three audiences. For policymakers: recognise democratic education as a core institutional responsibility, design funding models that support sustained engagement, and invest in educator professional development. For educational institutions: move from teaching about democracy to nurturing educational settings as sites of democracy, use the DHQ for participative self-assessment, and create conditions for sustained engagement through flexible timetabling and community partnerships. For educators: adopt co-creative, youth-centred approaches, develop relational skills as core professional competencies, and cultivate imagination through creative, artistic, and futures-oriented methods. Formative feedback on the DHQ further recommends the development of stronger action-oriented components to enable institutions to move from reflective self-assessment to concrete planning for improvement.

The CCLAB project has demonstrated that a well-designed pedagogical model, supported by sufficient duration, iterative design, and relational trust, can generate meaningful and in some cases transformative impacts on youth, educators, and organisations engaged in democratic education. The challenge going forward is to create the structural, institutional, and policy conditions that would allow these impacts to deepen, scale, and endure.

1. Introduction

1.1 About Critical ChangeLab

Critical ChangeLab (CCLAB) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project (April 2023 – March 2026) that aims to strengthen democracy in Europe through the creation and implementation of a flexible model of democratic pedagogy. The project brings together ten partner institutions (consortium members) across Europe, combining expertise from Arts and Humanities, Social Sciences, and Science and Technology in a transdisciplinary approach to democratic education.

CCLAB responds to growing evidence of youth disengagement from democratic institutions across Europe. Rather than treating democracy as an abstract concept to be taught, CCLAB embeds democracy as a lived, relational practice within both formal and non-formal educational settings. Through creative and narrative practices, including theatre of the oppressed, digital arts and media production, speculative design, zine-making and more, the project enables young people to critically examine global and local challenges, co-create knowledge, and take action in their immediate environments.

The CCLAB model is grounded in Participatory Action Research (PAR) principles, prioritising experiential learning, shared decision-making, and creative problem-solving. Over the course of the project, the model was developed iteratively through three cycles of participatory action research, implemented across Europe in more than 50 Critical ChangeLabs, engaging over 2,100 young people and 290 educators in collaboration with formal and non-formal education institutions and other partners including NGOs and creative and cultural industries. The project is grounded in the belief that meaningful participation in democracy-in-the-making requires not only theoretical understanding but also active experimentation and reflection.

1.2 Context of this deliverable within WP3: EVALUATE

This deliverable (D3.3) has been developed within Work Package 3 (WP3: EVALUATE), which encompasses the evaluation activities of the Critical ChangeLab project. WP3 comprises three complementary evaluation strands, each producing a dedicated deliverable:

- **D3.1 Critical ChangeLab Process and Recommendations for Practitioners** (Malinverni et al., 2026) examines the iterative design, implementation, and refinement of the CCLAB model across the three PAR cycles, providing evidence-based

recommendations for educators seeking to adopt and adapt the model in diverse educational contexts.

- **D3.2 Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation** (Durall et al., 2026) presents the final, refined version of the CCLAB model, consolidating the pedagogical framework, competence model, and implementation guidance that emerged from the iterative evaluation process.
- **D3.3 Critical ChangeLab Impact Evaluation** (Task 3.2, this deliverable) assesses the impact of the Critical ChangeLab project on its three key stakeholder groups (youth participants, educators, and consortium members) with particular attention to the development of democratic practices and transformative agency.
- **D3.4 Policy Recommendations based on the Socioeconomic Evaluation of the Critical ChangeLab Model** (Del Razo Martínez et al., 2026) examines the enabling and constraining factors for scaling and sustaining the model, analysing structural, relational, and affective dimensions alongside economic considerations to inform policy recommendations.

Where D3.1 focuses on *how* the model was developed and refined through practice, and D3.4 examines the *conditions* under which the model can be scaled and sustained, D3.3 addresses a distinct question: *what difference did the Critical ChangeLab project make?* This deliverable evaluates the project's impacts on the people and organisations involved, drawing on both qualitative and quantitative evidence to assess whether and how the intended impacts were realised.

1.3 Expected impacts and evaluation scope

CCLAB was designed to generate educational, civic, research and policy impacts by strengthening the relationship between young people and democracy in Europe. Responding to increasing democratic disengagement, the project aimed to cultivate young people's transformative agency: building their confidence, skills, and awareness needed to influence change and co-create democracy in everyday life. By making democratic processes visible and actionable, CCLAB sought to reinforce the foundations of European democracy through participatory, bottom-up, and justice-oriented educational approaches.

A central expected impact was the strengthening of active and inclusive citizenship among young people. By engaging youth with global and local issues relevant to their lived experiences, such as climate justice, technology, and social inequality, participants were

supported to connect democratic values with direct action in their immediate environments. This reframing of democracy as an everyday practice was intended to enable young people to recognise their capacity to influence social and political processes, addressing a key condition for sustained democratic participation.

At the level of education systems, the CCLAB model of democratic pedagogy was expected to strengthen democracy education across formal and non-formal learning environments, supporting inclusive and collaborative learning spaces in which democratic practices were enacted as well as taught. The project aimed to empower educators through participatory methods, creative practices, and tools for assessing democratic health, strengthening their capacity to foster youth agency and more democratic institutional cultures.

At the level of consortium members and local stakeholders, expected impacts included skills acquisition from involvement in running the project and local activities, changes to teaching and research approaches, capacity-building for critical democracy education by means of a community of practice, and the strengthening of partnerships and networks.

The project was also expected to produce significant research and policy-related impacts, including a robust comparative evidence base across ten European countries and validated tools such as the Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ) and Index. While the full evaluation of these outputs is beyond the scope possible within the timeframe of the funded project, they are expected to enhance institutions' and policymakers' capacity to assess and improve democratic practices in education and to inform evidence-based policy development at local, national, and EU levels.

Evaluation scope: T3.2 envisaged the impact evaluation drawing on feedback questionnaires from educators involved in training actions (T4.3, anticipated n=200) and interviews with youth taking part in mentoring actions through the MYCELIA programme (T4.3, anticipated n=10), plus interviews with representatives from all ten consortium partner organisations. Educator feedback was collected from 172 individuals: 89 respondents who participated in professional development workshops in Finland, Spain, Ireland and Croatia, 35 participants who completed the online CCLAB Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) entitled *Youth, democracy and technology - Participatory approaches for critical consciousness*¹ and 48 educators who participated in the project's Participatory Action Research (PAR) cycles. Youth interviews were conducted with three MYCELIA participants,

¹ The course can be accessed via this link: <https://digicampus.fi/course/view.php?id=5919> (account creation required)

reflecting the limited uptake of the mentoring programme (see Section 4.4 Limitations). To strengthen the evidence base, the evaluation also incorporates youth data from an interview with one member of the Youth Advisory Board, and analysis of data generated as part of the PAR cycles (researcher diaries and youth focus groups and reflective essays). Finally, the evaluation was enhanced through a review of relevant project deliverables. The data are discussed in detail in Chapter 2 (Methodology) and addressed in the limitations section of Chapter 4 (Discussion). Despite these adjustments, the evaluation provides a robust and multi-perspectival account of the project's impact across its three principal stakeholder groups.

1.4 Relationship to companion deliverables

This deliverable does not offer a description of the individual Critical ChangeLabs, as these are detailed in previous deliverables (D2.1 and D2.2: Laflin et al., 2025a; Laflin et al., 2025b and D3.1: Malinverni et al., 2026). Rather, this report draws on qualitative and quantitative data to evaluate the impact of the Critical ChangeLab project as a whole.

The deliverable is closely linked to several companion outputs across the project's work packages. Within WP3, D3.3 complements the CCLAB process evaluation (D3.1: Malinverni et al., 2026) by shifting the analytical focus from model refinement to impact assessment, and draws on the articulation of the final CCLAB pedagogical model (D3.2: Durall et al., 2026) as the framework against which impacts are contextualised. The socioeconomic evaluation presented in D3.4 (Del Razo Martínez et al., 2026) provides a complementary perspective on the structural and relational conditions required for the model's sustainability, and several of the findings in this report connect to the enabling and constraining factors identified there.

Beyond WP3, D3.3 is closely linked to the community empowerment and sustainability activities undertaken as part of Task 4.3 (WP4), which promoted the take-up of the project's results and outputs. The impact evaluation specifically assesses the reach and effects of these sustainability actions, including the educator training workshops and the MOOC. The Critical ChangeLab Educators' Handbook (D2.3) and the Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index (D1.1) are also relevant reference points, as both represent project outputs whose uptake and perceived value form part of the evidence considered in this evaluation.

1.5 Report overview

The remainder of this report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2 (Methodology)** sets out the mixed-methods approach utilised in evaluating the project's impacts on participating youth, educators, and consortium members. It describes the data sources, collection procedures, and analytical methods, and addresses ethical considerations.
- **Chapter 3 (Findings)** presents the results of the impact evaluation, organised by stakeholder group.
- **Chapter 4 (Discussion)** synthesises the findings across stakeholder groups, examines cross-cutting themes and patterns, applies an analytical framework to assess the nature and depth of impact, and addresses limitations of the evaluation.
- **Chapter 5 (Closing Remarks and Recommendations)** summarises the key findings and presents recommendations for policymakers, educational institutions, and educators, with attention to sustainability and alignment with current EU policy priorities.

2. Methodology

2.1 Impact evaluation approach

The central objective of this evaluation was to assess the impact of the Critical ChangeLab project on its three key stakeholder groups—youth participants, educators, and consortium members—with particular attention to the development of democratic practices and transformative agency. The evaluation was designed as a theory-based impact assessment, structured around the expected short-, medium- and long-term impacts articulated in the CCLAB Grant Agreement and collectively elaborated with the consortium members. This framing provided a deductive starting point for both data collection instrument design and analysis, while also allowing for the identification of unanticipated impacts that emerged inductively from the data.

A mixed-methods design was adopted, combining quantitative survey data with qualitative interview and observational data. This approach was chosen because the evaluation needed to capture both the breadth of impact across a large and diverse educator cohort (via surveys) and the depth and nuance of impact experiences among youth and consortium members (via semi-structured interviews). The integration of quantitative and qualitative strands follows established principles for mixed-methods research in programme evaluation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017) which emphasise adaptive, context-sensitive approaches to data collection and interpretation.

Data were collected between November 2025 and February 2026 from sources across the three stakeholder groups. These are described in the following subsections, and summarised in Table 1. This allowed for an adaptive approach to data collection and interpretation, in order to produce a grounded evaluation of the CCLAB project impacts.

2.2 Data sources

2.2.1 Educator data

Educator data were collected via surveys from three distinct cohorts, each representing a different mode and depth of engagement with the CCLAB project:

- **Educators – Training:** Educators who participated in short-term professional development workshops delivered by UOULU, UB, TCD and ISRZ. These covered pre-service and in-service teachers across primary, secondary, higher education, and

non-formal education sectors. Surveys were distributed following participation in these sessions (n=89).

- **Educators – MOOC:** Educators and other professionals who completed the CCLAB MOOC and filled out a survey as part of the accreditation process. Because the MOOC was open-access, this cohort includes respondents from outside the education sector. Details about the development and content of the MOOC are available in D4.3 (n=35).
- **Educators – PAR:** Educators who had previously been involved in a PAR Cycle as part of the CCLAB implementation. Surveys were distributed between 4 and 18 months after participation in a PAR cycle (n=48).

The surveys used for these cohorts (presented in Annex 1) were designed by the TCD research team, reviewed by all consortium members, and adapted for different contexts and languages before distribution to the respective cohorts. The instruments were designed to capture participants' understanding, confidence, preparedness and perceived ability to incorporate democratic education concepts and approaches into their work. Questions addressed three main areas. The first included confidence in supporting youth to engage with democracy in everyday contexts, including integrating democratic pedagogy into teaching, designing activities to help youth shape their futures, and seeing everyday democracy as relevant to the classroom. The second addressed preparedness to support youth agency in democratic learning, including engaging critically with digital platforms, taking meaningful action in communities, and understanding democracy as grounded in respect, inclusion and shared responsibility. The third dealt with expectations of implementing CCLAB methods in their future practice, including participatory action research with students, collaborative projects with community stakeholders, creative methods, the critical literacies framework, and imagining alternative futures.

The Educator (Training) and Educator (PAR) surveys comprised 14 Likert-scale questions, using a five-point confidence scale (Not at all confident to Very confident, including a neutral option) and a five-point likelihood scale (Very unlikely to Very likely, including a neutral option). The Educator (MOOC) survey covered similar areas but included additional questions to assess the specific outcomes of the MOOC: a checkbox question on the most meaningful and useful aspects of the programme, and three additional Likert-scale questions (five-point agreement scale, Strongly disagree to Strongly agree, including a neutral option) on respondents' ability to understand the intersectionality of democracy, the relevance of democratic engagement to their work, and their capacity to design activities that critically engage youth with social and technological issues. All three surveys also included short-answer open questions on anticipated challenges, supports and resources

needed for implementation, personal shifts in how respondents view democracy, likelihood of recommending the training to others, and intention to run a CCLAB in their own context.

2.2.2 Youth data

The youth evidence base for this evaluation comprises four semi-structured interviews and a systematic review of PAR Cycle 3 evaluation data from nine implementation locations.

Three individual online interviews were conducted with participants from the MYCELIA mentoring programme between December 2025 and January 2026. A fourth interview was conducted with a member of the Youth Advisory Board (YAB), who was involved in the project in an advisory capacity through a series of online meetings and an in-person workshop at the Ars Electronica Festival in 2025. These two groups had distinct experiences of the project: MYCELIA participants engaged in online near-peer mentoring on topics related to activism, planetary change and ethics, while the YAB member provided feedback on project decisions and directions and discussed the role of youth in democracy education more broadly.

T3.2 anticipated a sample of ten youth interviews drawn from an expected cohort of 40 youth involved in the MYCELIA mentorship programme (25% of overall sample). In practice, only five mentorships were completed by the end of January 2026, reflecting limited uptake of the programme. Three interviewees from this group represents 30% of the completed cohort. To supplement this small sample, the consortium invited members of the Youth Advisory Board to participate; despite multiple invitations, one member agreed. The implications of this small sample size are addressed in Section 4.4 (Limitations).

To complement the interview data, relevant records from the PAR Cycle 3 process evaluation (Task 3.1) were also drawn upon. Analysis notes from focus groups and educator interviews, as well as observational notes from researchers' diaries across nine locations, were reviewed using a deductive approach. These records were examined for evidence of expected youth impacts: increased skills and sociopolitical awareness, impact on critical and futures literacies, imagination and transformative agency, capacity for action, intention for future collaboration, and perceptions of the CCLAB programme. These data are used as a complementary source to contextualise and triangulate the individual interview findings, rather than as a direct measure of youth impact.

The semi-structured interview protocol is provided in Annex 1.

2.2.3 Consortium member data

To explore the impact of the project on consortium members and their wider networks, ten semi-structured interviews were conducted with representatives of each partner organisation between November and December 2025. The interviews comprised predefined open-ended questions (see Annex 1) and were conducted online using Zoom or Teams, and transcribed. The interview questions were developed to align with expected short-, medium- and long-term impacts in the CCLAB Grant Agreement, but also allowed respondents to take the conversation in directions they considered relevant, following methodological guidance on semi-structured interviews from Bryman (2016).

Table 1. Data sources for impact evaluation

Cohort	Data Collection Method	Sample size	Details
Youth	Semi-structured interviews	3	MYCELIA programme participants
Youth	Semi-structured interviews	1	Youth Advisory Board members
Educators	Survey	89	Educators – Training
	Survey	35	Educators – MOOC
	Survey	48	Educators – PAR Cycles
Consortium members	Semi-structured interviews	10	Organisational representatives
TOTAL PRIMARY RESPONDENTS		186	172 surveys + 14 interviews

To complement this primary data, researcher diaries and summaries of focus group interviews with youth participants from PAR cycles in nine locations were also reviewed as part of the dataset, as well as 19 additional reflective essays by youth in one location (UOULU).

2.3 Data Analysis

A combined deductive and inductive approach was used to analyse the data. A set of expected impacts were collectively developed within the consortium, providing an initial deductive framework for both the quantitative and qualitative analysis, while inductive coding allowed for the identification of themes and impacts not anticipated in advance. The deductive framework included transformative agency; democratic dispositions; sociopolitical awareness and knowledge; imagination, creativity and futures literacy; and practical impact.

Quantitative analysis. Survey responses were analysed using Excel. For Likert-scale questions, response frequencies were converted to percentages and the top two positive categories (e.g., Confident + Very Confident, or Likely + Very Likely) were merged to produce headline figures for each item. Cross-cohort comparisons between the three educator groups (Training, MOOC, PAR) were conducted using percentages to account for the different sample sizes. Checkbox and categorical questions were analysed by frequency. Where sample sizes vary across individual questions due to incomplete responses, the relevant n is reported in the findings.

Qualitative analysis. A thematic analysis approach was employed, following the six-phase framework of Braun and Clarke (2006) as elaborated by Castleberry and Nolen (2018). Two researchers from the TCD team conducted the analysis. Transcripts from the four youth interviews and ten consortium member interviews were first cross-checked with audio for accuracy, before being imported into NVivo software. In the first phase, transcripts were read in full to develop familiarity with the data. Initial codes were then generated deductively, guided by expected impact categories. A subsequent rounds of inductive coding was undertaken to search for additional themes in the data that were not captured by the initial framework. Codes were then reviewed, refined and organised into thematic clusters. A third researcher reviewed the codes and the team settled collectively on the final themes presented in Chapter 3.

Open-ended responses from the educator surveys were analysed using the same thematic structure developed from the youth and consortium member data as an initial guide, while remaining open to additional patterns. The PAR Cycle 3 evaluation data (analysis notes, focus group records and researcher diaries) were reviewed deductively, examining specifically for evidence of expected youth impacts as described in Section 2.2.2.

Findings are presented in Chapter 3 organised by stakeholder group, with impacts reported in order of frequency in the data. Qualitative findings are integrated with quantitative results within each thematic area.

2.4 Ethical Considerations

All data collected for this deliverable was gathered in accordance with institutional ethical approval granted by Trinity College Dublin (TCD), in line with the overall ethical framework governing the CCLAB project. This included informed consent procedures for all participants, with additional safeguards in place for research involving young people, such as parental or guardian consent and age-appropriate information sheets.

3. Findings

This chapter presents the results of the impact evaluation, organised by stakeholder group. For each group, impacts are presented in order of frequency in the data, followed by a summary of the main feedback on CCLAB programmes and activities. A discussion of these findings, including cross-cutting synthesis, analytical interpretation and limitations, follows in Chapter 4.

3.1 Impact on Youth

The youth impact findings draw on four semi-structured interviews (three MYCELIA participants and one Youth Advisory Board member) and PAR Cycle evaluation data from nine implementation locations, namely researcher reflection diaries, written summaries of focus groups, and summaries of interviews with educators. In addition, 19 reflective essays completed by youth who participated in a PAR Cycle in UOULU were included in this analysis. Three key themes were identified overall: impact on skills and personal strengths, impact on awareness and understanding and impact on capacity to take action, presented below.

Throughout this section, direct testimony from youth is distinguished from observations made by educators and researchers in the PAR cycle data. Where findings are drawn from the latter source, this is stated explicitly.

3.1.1 Impact on skills and personal strengths

All four interviewees reported positive impacts of the CCLAB project on the development of their skills and personal strengths and this was the area of impact most frequently observed across the broader youth data. Improved communication skills were the most frequently cited specific impact. Interviewees described better identification of target audiences for their activism work, improved design of communications materials such as videos and presentations, and increased knowledge of effective social media use. For example, one interviewee noted how the programme had taught them to consider both the intended audience and the purpose of the message when using different social networks.

Positive impacts on cooperation and connection skills were mentioned by two interviewees. In conversations with their mentors, youth noted they were better able to navigate differences of opinion. As one interviewee reflected, they felt they now listened in a more active way and could participate more fully in the listening process.

Researchers from four consortium member organisations noted similar changes among PAR Cycle 3 youth participants, particularly in terms of peer relationships and the ability to debate and disagree respectfully. Two of the four interviewees also reported that their self-confidence had increased and that they felt more motivated, self-sufficient and clearer about the action they wanted to take – as one noted, *“I feel like I could create even more change if given more opportunities.”* Three researchers noted similar improvements, particularly in participants’ confidence in speaking out and articulating their views. A positive impact on critical thinking was noted by one interviewee, particularly in adopting different perspectives and engaging in self-questioning about their understanding of democracy. Researchers and educators observed similar impacts on other youth participants in areas such as imaginative thinking (e.g., from session activities such as Speculative Futures – cf. Laflin et al., 2026) and critical awareness – e.g., how participants were able to notice the absence of democratic spaces available to them and also the impact of algorithms on freedom of choice.

3.1.2 Impact on awareness and understanding of democracy

Positive impacts on participants’ awareness and understanding of concepts related to everyday democracy were noted frequently in relation to power dynamics. Examples included the recognition of power dynamics and inequalities in students’ own schools and classes, as well as gaining a better understanding of life challenges facing young people, ethnic groups and others in different countries and cultures (e.g., those in the LGBTQ+ community, Palestinians). As one member of the Youth Advisory Board noted, *“... talking generally with young people from different countries, that was very, very resourceful, just because suddenly, you know, [I realised] okay, my life in Austria, it’s not standard. The most impactful thing for me was talking about how is it to be gay in Hungary? What’s that like, for example?”* – the realisation that their own experience was not universal, highlighting cross-cultural dialogue as one of the most impactful elements of the programme. Another youth in a PAR cycle focus group mentioned that CCLAB led them to understand that their voice *“matters”* and that *“people will listen to you if you have something to say”*. For others, increases in awareness and understanding were more related to specific knowledge gains: the relationship between digital technologies and politics, or the impact of disinformation on their lives, for example. Researchers from several consortium member organisations also noted increased awareness among youth participants of issues such as identity, justice, unequal access to power, and freedom of choice and expression. This is exemplified in research diaries in the following responses: *“It [the programme] showed [the participants] a clear awareness of their political surroundings and a critical view of who holds power in*

democratic processes” and “They [the participants] became more conscious of the absence of critical thinking and democratic spaces within their school system.”

Positive impacts on awareness and understanding of how democracy shows up in daily actions (i.e. 'everyday democracy') were reported by three interviewees, gained through CCLAB activities including workshops and conversations. Researchers from four consortium member organisations observed similar shifts, including examples of participants linking collaboration to democracy, using voting to resolve disagreements, and developing a clearer understanding of fairness, equality, voice and inclusion across groups. One such example was noted by an PAR Cycle participant in Oulu who participated in a programme related to AI: - *“Being in a room with people who had different mindsets and backgrounds ended up being one of the most valuable parts of the experience. We were constantly exchanging ideas, and I found myself learning not just from the content, but from the people around me”.*

A positive impact on awareness and understanding of change processes and ethics was reported by one of the interviewees, including their understanding of the role of media in democracy and limitations in the legal system. One researcher also noted increased awareness among youth participants of change over time in their local area, regarding elements such as history, power, access and justice. The evidence also suggests that some participants gained a deeper understanding of how democratic issues connect to wider society. For example, reflective essays from a PAR cycle in UOULU focused on AI included the following excerpts: *“I learned that AI systems are trained on data and follow specific rules and patterns, which means they can also reflect biases or errors depending on how they were built. Understanding this helped me see why it's important to be careful and thoughtful when developing or using AI systems, especially when they impact people's lives”,* and *“It helped me understand that AI isn't just about coding or math—it's about people, and the choices we make when we build or use technology. These presentations helped me realize how important it is to think critically about AI, not just accept it as 'neutral' or 'automatic'.”*

3.1.3 Impact on capacity to take action

Interviewees also reported an increase in their sense of personal agency and belief that they could create change. For example, one described how participation had increased their confidence and given them something tangible to show for their involvement: *“I would say it made me feel more satisfied with myself, because I sometimes feel like I'm kind of useless in real life... And by doing this, it has actually made me feel more confident with myself and it's something that I could actually put on my resume.”* All four interviewees reported positive impacts on their capacity to take action on issues relating to democracy.

One was actively engaged in identifying local organisations working in the area of addiction and had already started engaging with an informal student group taking action on climate change. Another had reached out to a community group active on the Palestine situation, describing how the programme had moved them from online engagement to real-life action: *"I've actually become more active in real life than before. Like, usually I just "like" comments, or just write some comments about the Gaza situation, but I've never actually taken action about it. So I think this programme has helped me take action".* Similar instances of positive impacts on agency and local action were noted by one researcher *"As I said, they're really activated - motivated is also not enough -, it's been like people come out very sort of passionate and with a sort of activist mindset."* In addition, during the consortium member interviews, one organisation highlighted how a CCLAB youth participant has gone on to become active in European Parliament youth discussions on civic education and advocacy.

3.1.4 Youth feedback on CCLAB programmes

All four interviewees provided feedback on their MYCELIA and Youth Advisory Board experiences. The most prominent theme concerned programme structure and activities. One interviewee felt they would have liked greater visibility of how their participation contributed to outcomes. They also suggested that having young people involved on the organisation side, not just as participants or guests, could make the experience less intimidating, noting that the professional, adult-led format of some interactions created a sense of distance: *"Sometimes it was a bit difficult to connect - it was adult people, very professional, very business, asking us those questions, and that was a bit intimidating. Maybe it would be a bit easier if it felt like there was also a young person on your end."* The same interviewee suggested that even more creative engagement opportunities such as video-making, collaging and poetry would allow participants to express themselves more individually. Two interviewees felt their expectations of the mentorship were met and that it provided constructive support, while another would have liked the opportunity to continue sessions with their mentor after the programme concluded, saying that *"I'm asking if I could still follow this [the MYCELIA mentorship programme], because I think this programme is pretty interesting for me."*

Feedback contained in the PAR cycle evaluation extracts data source echoed several of these themes. Researchers and educators most frequently commented on the value of interactive, hands-on learning, creative activities and making, and critical and futures thinking. One researcher noted that young people were highly motivated by tangible, hands-on projects that allowed for immediate results and creative expression - *"Their*

ability to troubleshoot, refine, and improve their creations showcased a practical and iterative approach to transforming ideas into reality.” The personal sharing of perspectives and emotions was also seen as improving participant engagement and helping youth to express their values and political concerns.

These themes also appeared in data from a PAR cycle organised by UOULU in which participants explored issues relating to AI (the ‘AI Ambassador’ programme). In their reflective essays participants noted both the difficulty and the positive learning outcomes that emerge from working with unfamiliar digital tools. One participant described finding a particular tool unintuitive at first, but reflected that *“not every part of a learning experience will be easy or smooth, but with the right attitude, you can still make it work”*. Participants frequently mentioned the social aspects of their learning and recognised the importance of engaging with their peers. As one wrote, *“I had the opportunity to talk a lot with my group, which was one of the best parts of the experience.... [we] shared our thoughts during discussions and supported each other when things got confusing. These conversations helped me see different perspectives and made me more aware of the social side of AI. It was great to learn from others.”*

3.2 Impact on Educators

Completed surveys were received from a total of 169 educator respondents: 89 for the Educators (Training) survey, 48 for the Educators (PAR) survey, and 35 for the Educators (MOOC) survey. Sample sizes vary slightly across individual survey questions due to incomplete responses; where this occurs, the relevant n is reported in the figure caption.

The majority of Educator (Training) respondents were from the secondary education sector (55%), while the majority of Educator (PAR) respondents were from the secondary or non-formal education sector (37% each). The Educator (MOOC) respondents had more varied backgrounds: formal education (32%), technology development (29%), non-formal/informal education (18%), youth work (6%) and other areas (15%). This variation among MOOC respondents is likely attributable to the open-access nature of the MOOC, in contrast to the trainings and PAR cycles which were offered exclusively to individuals working or training to work in the education sector.

Figure 1: Survey respondents by educational sector they work or expect to work in. (Educators (Training) n=89, Educators (PAR) n=48).

Figure 2: Survey respondents by educational sector (Educator (MOOC) n=35)

Analysis of the Educator (Training) and Educator (PAR) surveys each contained 14 Likert-type scale questions covering three areas: participants' confidence in integrating democratic pedagogy into their practice, the likelihood of their implementing specific CCLAB approaches in their future work, and their preparedness to support young people's engagement with democracy in everyday contexts (Annex 1). The majority of responses across all questions fell in the top two categories (i.e. Confident or Very Confident, Likely or Very Likely, Agree or Totally Agree depending on the question) indicating a generally positive response to CCLAB training across all three areas. A similar pattern was observed in the Educator (MOOC) survey, in which the majority of responses also fell in the top two categories for 11 of 12 Likert-type scale questions relating to the same three areas. A

consistent pattern is observable across cohorts: educators with deeper engagement in the project (PAR cohort) tended to report higher confidence and likelihood scores with regards to implementing CCLAB approaches than those with shorter exposure (MOOC and Training). Findings from the quantitative and qualitative data related to educators are grouped under the following headings.

3.2.1 Impact on skills and personal strengths

Impact on skills

Across six survey questions relating to skills (design activities; integrate approaches; support students to take local action / engage critically with digital platforms), respondents in all three cohorts reported positive impacts. A significant majority felt confident or very confident about being able to integrate democratic pedagogy and ideas and approaches from CCLAB into their own work (83% MOOC, 85% Training, 91% PAR - Figure 3). A high majority also reported feeling confident or very confident about designing activities to help youth critically engage with and shape their futures (73% MOOC, 86% Training, 86% PAR). For example, one respondent noted how *“This course equipped me with good understanding of how digital tools can enhance civic participation in a democratic way”*, while another felt that they *“learnt a lot about how technologies work and how to facilitate workshops.”*

Figure 3: Distribution of educator responses to the statement “I understand how to integrate democratic pedagogy in my teaching,” by cohort (Educator (Training) n=89, Educator (PAR) n=48, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

Figure 4: Distribution of educator responses to the statement "I can design learning activities that help youth recognise their ability to shape their futures and make a difference, changing things for the better," by cohort (Educator (Training) n=89, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

The majority of respondents also reported a high or very high likelihood of implementing specific tools and approaches from the CCLAB in their workplace: participatory action research with students (64% MOOC, 82% PAR, 84% Training – Figure 5); creative methods to explore democratic activities (70% MOOC, 82% PAR, 84% Training – Figure 6); the critical literacies framework (79% MOOC, 79% Training, 80% PAR) and imagining alternative futures with students (75% MOOC, 85% Training, 91% PAR).

Figure 5: Distribution of educator responses on likelihood of implementing participatory action research with students, by cohort (Educator (Training) n=84, Educator (PAR) n=48, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

Figure 6: Distribution of educator responses on likelihood of implementing creative methods to explore democratic ideas, by cohort (Educator (Training) n=89, Educator (PAR) n=46, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

Impact on personal strengths

Educator respondents reported high or very high levels of confidence in their capacity to support youth engagement with democracy in everyday contexts after their training (74% Training, 89% PAR). A related question in the MOOC survey showed that 73% of respondents felt they had the capacity to design activities helping youth critically engage with social and technological issues. A high majority across all three cohorts also reported feeling confident or very confident about being prepared to support young people in understanding democracy as a way of living based on respect, inclusion and shared responsibility. As one respondent noted, *“The deep-seated problems of youth have become relatable to me, and technological advances no longer frighten me.”*

Figure 7: Distribution of educator responses on confidence in supporting youth to engage with democracy in everyday contexts, by cohort (Educator (Training) n=89, Educator (PAR) n=48, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

Figure 8: Distribution of educator responses on confidence in supporting young people to understand democracy as a way of living and interacting with others based on respect, inclusion, and shared responsibility, by cohort (Educator (Training) n=89, Educator (PAR) n=48, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

3.2.2 Impact on awareness and understanding

The majority of respondents reported high or very high levels of confidence in their ability to see everyday democracy as relevant to their teaching practice (83% PAR, 91% MOOC, 93% Training). They also felt prepared or very prepared to support young people to recognise the relationship between democracy and technology (70% Training, 79% MOOC, 86% PAR). In addition, a significant majority of MOOC respondents (88%) felt prepared to support young people to engage critically with digital platforms as citizens.

Figure 9: Distribution of educator responses to the statement “I see everyday democracy as relevant to classroom practice,” by cohort (Educator (Training) n=89, Educator (PAR) n=48, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

The MOOC survey contained a specific question on whether respondents had experienced a personal shift in how they view the relationship between youth, democracy, and technology as a result of the course. Of those who responded, 69% reported a positive shift, 22% reported no shift, and the remaining 9% responded neutrally. Positive shifts included this perspective from one respondent: *“I experienced a personal shift in how I view that relationship because I underestimated the transformative impact of democracy, provided it is taught in a proper, age-appropriate way.”* The positive shifts reported included the reframing of technology, as not just a tool but an intrinsic aspect of democracy and everyday life which can empower or disempower youth voices. Respondents also highlighted how they now think more critically about how best to support their students in this regard and are more encouraging of the efforts of youth to become more politically active. As one respondent noted, *“I better understand that young people are not just users of technology, but active citizens who can question and change digital systems. It is important to give students more space to discuss, reflect, and take action on real social issues.”* Some reported shifts in critical awareness of their own digital media and technology use. For example, one respondent noted how *“I used to think that “youth participation in democracy” mainly meant voting, joining clubs, or go parade, technology was just a tool for sending messages or sharing news. After taking this course, I’ve come to realize that technology itself shapes who gets heard, how information is seen, and whether discussions get derailed, it’s actually part of democracy, not just a tool.”* Overall, these positive shifts

indicate a greater sense of responsibility for supporting students' critical engagement with technology and digital media.

3.2.3 Impact on capacity for action and collaboration

A majority of respondents felt confident or very confident about their preparedness to support young people to plan and take meaningful action in their local communities (73% PAR, 75% Training, 79% MOOC). For example, respondents noted that *“It is important to give students more space to discuss, reflect, and take action on real social issues.”* A high majority also felt confident about the likelihood of implementing collaborative projects with external community stakeholders in the future (75% Training, 80% PAR, 65% MOOC).

Figure 10: Distribution of educator responses on confidence in supporting young people to plan and take meaningful action in their local communities, by cohort (Educator (Training) n=87, Educator (PAR) n=47, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

Figure 11: Distribution of educator responses on likelihood of implementing collaborative projects involving external community stakeholders, by cohort (Educator (Training) n=83, Educator (PAR) n=47, Educator (MOOC) n=35)

3.2.4 Feedback on training utility, challenges and supports

The MOOC survey contained three questions on respondents' views regarding the most meaningful aspects of the training, the challenges they anticipated, and the supports they felt would help integrate their learning into practice.

The two most meaningful aspects identified were critically reflecting on the relationship between technology and democracy (66%) and learning about new activities and methods (60%). For example, one educator noted that *"The most meaningful aspect was learning how creative, participatory methods can help youth critically reflect on technology and democracy in ways that are grounded in everyday experience and local contexts.* Another highlighted how the programme complemented other training they were taking: *"I was also independently of this course taking two courses on AI and Big Data. Seeing how much useful overlap there was made me even more motivated to engage with all courses. I also appreciated all the external links and resources and actually admired the amount of resources included. Exploring those on their own was fun, engaging and educating."* A further 37% of respondents highlighted both the discovery of new case studies and the ability to connect module content with their own work.

In terms of anticipated challenge in applying programme approaches, 57% highlighted time, space and resource constraints, and institutional or policy barriers. These included issues such as access to the required technology, inflexible timetables and resistance from

staff or families, and rigid curricula. A further 31% highlighted gaps in their professional development or capacity, while 26% were concerned about constraints on student agency and transforming ideas into action.

Respondents equally highlighted three priority areas for support, each highlighted by 51% of respondents: the need for open-access materials, resources, teaching guides; institutional support in the form of protected teaching time and job security for democracy education facilitators; and access to a community network for project implementation and mentorship. Professional development opportunities were identified as potentially beneficial by 48% of respondents.

When asked about their intent to run a Critical ChangeLab in their own classroom, 38% of Educator (Training) and 33% of Educator (PAR) respondents said yes, while only 4% and 3% respectively said no. The majority indicated they were not sure (58% Training, 64% PAR). Those who said no cited systemic barriers such as time restrictions, limited resources, and a lack of institutional support. Those who said yes described a variety of implementation routes, including extracurricular projects and integration into existing curricula such as history or citizenship education. Several described ambitious plans for participatory dynamics, artistic projects, and debate spaces oriented toward social justice and democratic participation. One respondent captured the rationale clearly: they would implement a CCLAB in their school *“because it creates a meaningful learning environment where young people feel heard and empowered, ”* grounded in topics relevant to students' daily lives, using *“digital tools and group activities to make it engaging, and create a safe space where everyone can contribute. ”*

A significant majority across all cohorts indicated they were likely or very likely to recommend their CCLAB training to others (85% Training, 88% MOOC, 89% PAR). Reasons included the importance of topics addressing youth, democracy and technology; access to well-structured tools and resources; learning opportunities around critical thinking; and the potential for perspective-broadening. One respondent said they *“would recommend this MOOC because it encourages critical thinking about technology, democracy, and participation in a clear and accessible way. The case examples make the concepts concrete and relevant. It is especially useful for students and educators interested in civic engagement and digital society.”* Another noted how *“The course combines theory with practical case examples, which helped me reflect on my own teaching and how I can better support young people as active, critical participants in democracy. It’s well-structured, easy to follow, and valuable for anyone working in education or youth work.”* In addition, another respondent highlighted the unique value the programme provided compared to other

training: *"I would recommend it to other students because it's a very important and interesting topic, which I have actually not really seen in any other academic courses that I have taken before."*

These anticipated challenges were echoed in observations from the PAR cycle evaluation data, where researchers and educators identified similar structural constraints in practice. Three researchers highlighted that in CCLABs delivered in formal education settings, pre-existing class dynamics, classroom practices and timetabling constraints affected engagement, group dynamics and decision-making. As one researcher noted, *"... many participants have internalized a top-down understanding of e.g. school life where teachers are responsible to make decisions."* The challenge of achieving meaningful impact in cases where there were only three CCLAB sessions with young people was also highlighted, pointing to a design tension within some versions of the CCLAB model: the need for extended time to work with youth on complex topics, which is not always possible within institutional or project-based constraints.

Four researchers indicated that existing authority dynamics could hinder facilitation and constrain the potential for engagement and transformation. Other issues raised included the need to ensure sufficient critical understanding of key topics before youth engaged in activities such as debates, as well as how to provide for sustained engagement beyond programme sessions. In addition, some educators also noted the need for clear and tangible structuring of imagination and futures-related tasks to enhance engagement and also the building-in of time for structured reflection to sustain such engagement. Finally, the importance of clearly articulating intended outcomes at the start to maximise engagement was noted, as was the impact of limited language proficiency on participation in some contexts.

3.3 Impact on Critical ChangeLab Consortium Members

Analysis of the consortium member interview transcripts indicated four key areas of impact. These are presented below, followed by a summary of challenges.

3.3.1 Impact on partnerships, networks and collaboration

All ten consortium members reported positive impacts on partnerships and networks, with 66 instances of impact recorded across the transcripts. These were identified at four levels.

Institutional level

Positive impacts at institutional level were reported by two consortium members, whereby they increased their networking and collaboration with colleagues from other departments. For one organisation, this took the form of informal conversations and information-sharing between researchers, leading to increased awareness of synergies between their work, as well as shared activities and joint publications. For the other, their presence within an existing research centre in their institution was strengthened, as was their relationship with a technology and ethics group, with whom future collaboration is likely.

Community and local level

Across the lifetime of the three-year CCLAB project, the consortium engaged in with collaborations with 52 formal and 46 non-formal education institutions, as well as 58 external partners (CCLAB D3.4: Del Razo Martínez et al., 2026). These included local government, youth services, universities, civil society organisations, NGOs, creative and artistic associations, the technology sector and other organisations interested in democracy issues. Seven consortium members reported positive impacts at community and local level. For some, participation in the CCLAB project enabled the formalisation of longer-term relationship development with schools rather than previous one-off workshops, as well as increased opportunities for new collaborations with a diverse range of organisations in new fields of activity. There was also an expansion of outreach beyond the usual established school networks to other youth settings. Increased access for young people to resources and services provided by universities, NGOs and other organisations was highlighted as another positive impact - for example, one consortium member described an initiative that involved bringing the project to a new location in the city centre to show young people that these are services they could access independently. Another highlighted their engagement with external organisations during the PAR cycles: *"We had visits from the high city officials who would come and speak to the young people, we had ex-addicts coming to the group that was dealing with addiction. We had a theatre play*

being organised by the student home for them on addiction. We also had young people going to the university counselling services and experiencing counselling."

National level

Six consortium members reported national-level impacts, including the extension of partnerships or collaborations with teacher training organisations beyond regional level; participation in national fora on democracy and regional European networks; and participation in national seminars and conferences. One consortium member reported how collaboration with an NGO working in the area of politics and elections opened up an entirely new target group for them of young people interested in democracy. Another benefitted from membership of a national research centre for future networks and communications which grew from collaboration on a CCLAB PAR Cycle and also led to a new collaboration with a national organisation promoting Indigenous language and heritage in education.

European level

Seven consortium members experienced positive impacts from the project at European level, including the value of connecting – and in some cases, re-connecting – with high-profile partners across Europe working on aligned topics. This resulted in both a strengthening and expansion of networks in related research fields. For example, one member reported that *"because we have been collaborating with other consortium specific deliverables throughout the project with different levels of engagement and I think besides the consortium itself, we have built some stronger partnerships and relationships with these organisations."* The expertise and high-profile of some partners in the field of youth and education was particularly appreciated. In addition, there were opportunities to join European-wide networks in areas such as civic education. There were also opportunities for collaborative activities such as a policy roundtable at a democracy conference with other Horizon Europe projects DEMOCRAT and AECED (funded under the same call as CCLAB), and the sharing of expertise between consortium member organisations.

Potential for future collaboration

All ten consortium members reported that the CCLAB project has generated potential opportunities for future collaboration on research and practice work, both with the consortium network and with other local and national organisations that they worked with during the project. As one member noted, *"I think things that we have done and things that partners have done have allowed us to get to know each other a little bit better and... having had the experience of working together, I definitely see a lot of correlations or opportunities*

to work beyond just for the sake of the consortium.” Five of the consortium members already have specific future projects in preparation with contacts they made through the CCLAB project, while two others said that the project has resulted in invitations to participate in future projects. The remaining three said that they are very interested in collaborating with other consortium members and new contacts they made, and feel that the project has given them a good basis to pursue this, especially in terms of being able to identify potential new collaboration opportunities.

3.3.2 Impact on organisational skills, learning and resources

Across nine consortium member interviews, 67 instances of organisational impact were recorded, falling into three main areas.

Team learning and perspective shifts

Nine consortium member organisations reported positive impacts on their teams’ learning and perspectives. For example, four became aware of the potential to expand their organisation’s focus on democracy-related issues, while five felt they now had the potential to increase their reach among different youth cohorts and groups. There was also learning about opportunities to deepen discussions about the future of European education and democratic participation, as well as the value of including youth perspectives in these discussions. For one organisation, there was the realisation that making the topic of democracy relevant to young people’s lives provides an interesting entry point to working with them. For another, CCLAB offered an opportunity to expand their approach to democracy education to include an historical and heritage perspective alongside futures thinking, as well as new insights about the need to support young people from less well-off backgrounds to develop leadership skills.

Consortium members were also able to increase their organisational reach to other youth demographic profiles, as well as to non-school settings. In some cases, this has resulted in a shift in strategic thinking about how best to approach and work with young people. For example, one noted how the project *“made us aware of the idea that democracy is a very important topic to bring up with youth, especially in relation to our mission that is more about technology and society but [that] democracy education plays a very a huge role in this. So, I think the change or the difference is that we are proactively looking for projects that that involve democracy education now.”* In addition, there has been learning from other consortium members in terms of gaining both a cross-European perspective and a cross-disciplinary perspective, with the involvement of academic, civil society and other partner organisations in the project. Internally, consortium members reported a better alignment of

organisational work areas, for example integrating democracy and citizenship education into existing work on digital technologies and child-computer interaction for one consortium member.

There have also been opportunities to embed learning from using project tools consistently over the three-year duration. Three organisations also highlighted how the relatively longer project duration was instrumental in facilitating and supporting deeper learning, as there have been more opportunities for reflection, discussion and then operationalisation of the learning than usually happens with shorter projects. Having time to reflect on the outcomes of each PAR cycle and learn from other consortium members' experiences in each cycle was mentioned as a benefit: *"I think what really helped were the iterative cycles... you have the opportunity for iterations, testing different ideas, you could follow the same kind of path but also change it. So that that kind of framework was really helpful for us, really great - the three iterative cycles were great and this really helped."*

Team skills development

Eight of the ten organisations reported that the CCLAB project impacted positively on the skills development of staff involved in the project team. For example, there was the acquisition of facilitation and teaching skills resulting from utilisation of the CCLAB methodologies and practices, especially for non-formal settings such as workshops and engaging directly with young people. For example, one member, referring to the PAR cycle activities with young people, noted how *"we really had hands-on moments in which we've learned a lot about the implications and the interest of youth within democracy. So for sure we will continue relying into the practices and also the materials that that have been produced."* The development of skills in evaluation and in identifying project impact was also reported. Some reported becoming more skilled in identifying potential collaborators, and in the selection and the upskilling of junior team members, including doctoral researchers. Other positive impacts reported included an increase in team understanding of youth perspectives on democracy as a result of participation in the PAR cycles; the creation of institutional memory around learnings taken from the project which can be applied to the design of future projects, including funding applications; and an improvement of research competencies (e.g. from production of the Democracy Health Index). As one member noted, *"It [participation in the project] made us rethink how we approach doing workshops, for educators, obviously, but also for us as an institution, how to think more about picking partner institutions and how to adapt it to different contexts. I think we stepped a bit out of our comfort zone of doing things this way."* The availability of CCLAB resources for use in future staff training and project design was also regarded as a

positive impact. Overall, the project has enabled consortium members to bring certain skills in-house as a result of participation in the project, as their teams developed skills which previously had to be outsourced.

Employment and other resource impacts

Six consortium members reported a positive impact on organisational resources from the project. Four were able to hire a new staff member to work on the project, while two said the project funding enabled them to retain an existing staff member. One also described how their access to new networks because of participation in the project resulted in funding becoming available to develop teacher resources on democracy and support the young people who were participating in project activities. Additional positive impacts were mentioned by two other organisations, such as the benefit of the project being very well-managed by the coordinators and the opportunity to work longer-term on the topic of democracy from both a local / national perspective and a European one (via the project consortium members), especially since this topic can be a struggle to obtain funding for. As one member noted, *“Implementation, even in the two-year projects tends to take place for 2-3 months and prior to that you’re doing your research, you’re kind of growing your network, then you do the evaluation. But here you have the opportunity over three years to do the actions and refine them and you had continuous support over [that time].”* The positive learning impacts from the iterative PAR cycles were again highlighted, along with the need to ensure that the project outputs and contacts are available after the project concludes.

3.3.3 Impact on current or planned activity

Eight consortium members reported 23 positive impacts on their current and future research and projects.

Four reported specific impacts on current work, including the application of project methods in other projects and workshops, the embedding of CCLAB approaches in teacher education programmes, and the combination of CCLAB elements with other Horizon Europe project outputs. Eight spoke about future impacts, including the incorporation of power structures and democracy into citizenship education, new STEAM and decolonial approaches to critical literacy, improved skills for educator training, better mapping of potential partner organisations, and in one case, a city council decision to fund an extension of the CCLAB and PAR cycles to ensure sustainable impact.

3.3.4 Impact on teaching, facilitation and working with young people

Five consortium members highlighted 17 ways in which the project impacted their teaching and interaction with young people. These ranged from changes to teaching practices resulting from experiences in the PAR cycles and using new activities and methods of youth engagement, to higher-level reflections on how to better plan for more youth engagement in the future. Specific areas of impact included the value of having external practice partners who can open channels of communication with youth audiences, tools for improving facilitation expertise and resolving conflicts, and the integration of CCLAB workshops into teacher education programmes on related topics like Global Citizenship Education. Two organisations reported positive impacts on their critical understanding of the importance of including democracy in education programmes, as well as a more reflective approach to their practical education work, with one noting *"... we would never have really used the term democracy in any of our education programmes and I think this is recognising that it's something that's important for young people and it's important [in terms of] contributing as a civic organisation to strengthen everything. So, it has changed our perception of the value of participatory practices."*

3.3.5 Challenges

Six of the ten consortium members reported on challenges they experienced during the project. The most common were time and flexibility constraints (five organisations), with three mentioning that they didn't have sufficient time to fully explore with participants certain topics which arose during the PAR cycles, such as racism or the crisis in Palestine. One noted: *"I think we tried to put too much into the PAR cycles, and I think that we put too many barriers and restrictions on what a PAR cycle would look like in terms of it having to be six sessions or eight sessions and there having to be this many hours. Often, that's not really possible when you work with young people, especially when you work with schools or with non-formal organisations."* Two felt that the condensed nature of the activities meant that students were unable to acquire a sufficiently deep understanding of how concepts such as democracy evolve over time. One also felt that it could be more beneficial to work more deeply with one group for a year, instead of three different groups over the project duration.

Timing was also an issue in relation to the fact that youth participants were involved in other activities which sometimes made it difficult for them to attend; for example, the difficulty of having to hold events during the summer, when young people are on holidays was noted. In terms of flexibility, one interviewee felt it would have been beneficial to have had more exchange of practices and activities between consortium members during the project.

Another mentioned occasional differences in expectation between their own desire to co-create activities with youth participants and the host organisation expecting content and programmes to be pre-packaged or developed in advance. Another consortium member was of the view that the very ambitious nature of the project – especially aiming to apply the CCLAB in formal and non-formal learning settings – was a struggle to implement at times, particularly in terms of supporting a more bottom-up approach. However, they also felt that their experiences of running the labs within these constraints could feed into future guidance for this process.

Four consortium members separately identified a perceived difference between research and practice partners in their understanding and use of terminology relating to central concepts, which they felt might have benefitted from more effective consensus-building at the early stages of the project. Linked to this was a perceived need to better support practice partners to showcase their approaches and contributions, which may differ from those of research partners.

3.4 Formative Feedback on the Democracy Health Questionnaire

In addition to the impact evaluation findings presented in Sections 3.1–3.3, formative feedback was gathered on one of the project's key research outputs: the Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ). Three focus groups were conducted to assess participants' experiences of completing the questionnaire and to identify issues relating to item clarity, comprehension, and structure. The full analysis is presented in Annex 2. The most notable finding was that while participants consistently valued the DHQ as a tool for structured reflection on democratic practices, they identified a need for the instrument to incorporate stronger action-oriented dimensions – enabling institutions not only to assess their democratic health but to plan concrete steps for improvement. This finding is taken up in the recommendations in Chapter 5.

4. Discussion

4.1 Cross-Cutting Impacts

The findings presented in Chapter 3 reveal that the CCLAB project has generated a substantial body of positive impacts across all three stakeholder groups: youth participants, educators, and consortium partners. Three cross-cutting areas of impact are visible across these groups, indicating that the project was effective in reinforcing core outcomes. These are: impacts on skills and personal strengths; impacts on awareness and understanding of everyday democracy and related issues; and impacts on capacity for action, collaboration, and future activity.

That these three areas of impact emerged consistently across groups with very different roles, contexts, and levels of engagement with the project is noteworthy. Youth participants, educators undergoing initial or continuing professional development, and organisational partners all reported growth in broadly comparable domains, as appropriate to their contexts. This convergence suggests that the CCLAB model's participatory, creative, and critically reflective design operated as a coherent pedagogical approach capable of generating impacts at multiple levels simultaneously.

A number of common challenges were also identified, including time and resource constraints, structural rigidities in formal education settings, and the difficulty of sustaining engagement and deeper outcomes beyond programme sessions. These challenges are explored further in Section 4.3 below.

4.2 Transformational potential of the Critical ChangeLab project impacts

A key focus of the CCLAB project was to enable the development of youth and educators' transformative agency. Given this, there is value in using a transformation lens to categorise and discuss the key project impacts identified in the impact evaluation analysis. This is done below using the Three Orders of Change framework (Bartunek and Moch, 1987), which distinguishes three levels or 'orders' of change, along the trajectory from supporting the status quo to systemic transformation and which originated in research on institutional transformation.

First-order change generally involves incremental modifications to practices, actions or behaviours within existing structures and paradigms (Bartunek & Moch, 1987). It can include

things like modifying existing research methods (Krawczyk et al., 2025) or working to increase the diversity of an institution's workforce (Culpepper et al., 2025). Second-order change seeks deeper change in practices and relationships and some modification of existing structures, such as changing research culture, forming networks beyond the institution and creating a culture of inclusion (ibid). Third order change goes beyond this to generate a still-deeper examination of institutional, collective and /or individual culture, values, paradigms, etc., which often unconsciously lie at the root of barriers to change. It aims to unlock the potential for transformation at all three levels, thereby supporting truly transformative outcomes (Sterling, 2011; Slater et al., 2022; Wahl & Rudinger, 2025). It requires significant effort and commitment and often faces resistance, especially in relation to the shifting of mindsets and values (Krawczyk et al., 2025).

The framework - and modifications of it - have been applied to identify and evaluate transformative potential and impacts in a range of fields, including food systems (Slater et al., 2022), healthcare (Olaitan, 2024; Krawczyk et al., 2025), academic workplaces (Culpepper et al., 2025) and sustainability transitions (Manniche & Skriver Hansen, 2025). These applications demonstrate its utility as a diagnostic tool for understanding both instances in which change has occurred, and what kind of change it represents - a distinction that is particularly important for projects, like CCLAB, that aspire to transformative rather than merely incremental outcomes.

Authors such as Barth and Michelsen (2013) and Wahl and Rudinger (2025) have applied the framework to sustainability education, where they categorise approaches as education about sustainability (first-order change) involving content-based sustainability literacy or knowledge acquisition; education for sustainability (second-order change) being the ability to put this knowledge into practice and the questioning of assumptions; and education as sustainability (third order change) relating to shifting values, systems thinking and expansive worldviews in support of thriving planetary futures. In their work linking sustainability science and education for sustainable development, Mochizuki and Yarime (2015) further show how these levels can be applied to emerging practices in complex sustainability science, particularly to conceptualise multi-, inter- and transdisciplinarity. By this view, multidisciplinary involves assembling relevant knowledge to address complex challenges while remaining within a single disciplinary boundary; interdisciplinarity further connects and integrates disciplinary knowledge and expertise; while transdisciplinarity involves mutual learning across and beyond disciplinary boundaries and roles. Similar three-level models that expand knowledge generation beyond typical domains have been identified for science (Irwin, 2021) and science communication (Achiam & Irwin, 2025).

This trend towards increasingly diverse, inclusive and open modes of knowledge generation resonates with broader debates in democratic citizenship education. Gert Biesta (2024), for instance, distinguishes between three domains of purpose of education: socialization of learners into existing democratic norms, education that equips them with civic knowledge and skills (qualification), and education that supports subjectification – the emergence of the learner as an independent political subject capable of democratic action. Westheimer and Kahne (2004) also identify three conceptions of citizenship education: personally responsible, participatory, and justice-oriented – with only the last of these oriented toward the structural analysis and collective action that characterise deeper democratic engagement.

Adapting these categories for the CCLAB project can allow for the impacts above – and their transformative potential – to be discussed as follows:

- Impacts **about** democracy (first-order change): development of content, resources and activities; organisational benefits.
- Impacts **for** democracy (second-order change): skills development, capacity building, expanded networks, and enhanced awareness enabling participants to act on their learning.
- Impacts **as** democracy (third-order change): ontological shifts in beliefs, values and assumptions that open up the possibility of systemic transformation.

The following subsections discuss the project's impacts at each of these three levels, drawing on the findings from youth, educator, and consortium member data presented in Chapter 3.

4.2.1 Impacts about democracy (first-order change)

Elements of first-order change – or impacts *about* democracy – can be seen in several areas of the CCLAB project's outcomes. These relate to modifications of existing practices, actions or behaviours. A clear example is the planned uptake of the content developed for the PAR cycles (cf. Laflin et al., 2026), the Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy (Durall et al., 2026) and the CCLAB MOOC by consortium members in their work across formal and non-formal education sectors. The MYCELIA and Youth Advisory Board elements also provided opportunities for youth participants to access support and mentorship. Opportunities for consortium members and educators to embed democracy and critical literacy-related themes in initial teacher education represent another positive impact at this level, as do the organisational resource benefits reported by consortium

members, such as staffing capacity, which are enabling them to broaden and deepen the scope of their work with young people on democracy-related topics.

These first-order impacts are important as foundational contributions. They describe the infrastructure of citizenship education – the materials, programmes, and organisational conditions that make democratic learning possible. They correspond to the *qualification* function of education identified by Biesta (2024), namely the transmission and acquisition of knowledge, skills, and understandings. Without these practical and material foundations, the deeper forms of change discussed below would have no base from which to develop.

However, challenges identified in the impact evaluation reveal the limits of first-order change when operating within unsupportive structures. Inflexibility in formal education settings impacted on the range and depth of activities that could be carried out. Time, space, and resource constraints were cited by all three stakeholder groups. A lack of younger staff on the organisational side may also have constrained youth participants' self-confidence and level of engagement. Together, these challenges reflect a key characteristic of first-order change: the focus remains on *what* is being done and the practical barriers that support or suppress activity, rather than on interrogating the structures themselves.

4.2.2 Impacts for democracy (second-order change)

Elements of second-order change – or impacts *for* democracy – can also be identified across the CCLAB project's outcomes, where deeper changes in practices and relationships were generated. Building on the resources and content developed at the first-order level, all three stakeholder groups reported the acquisition of new skills. For youth participants, these included communication, listening, critical thinking, and cooperation skills. Educators reported increased confidence in implementing participatory action research, creative methods, critical literacies, and futures-based approaches in their work. Consortium members highlighted the development of facilitation and teaching skills, improvements in research competencies, and enhanced capacity for engaging with young people.

Alongside these practical skills, significant shifts in personal strengths and awareness were reported. Youth participants described an increase in their sense of agency and self-confidence in relation to initiating change. Educators reported increased confidence in supporting young people to engage with social and technological issues and to act with respect and shared responsibility. These shifts resonate with Mezirow's (1997) concept of *perspective transformation* in transformative learning theory, whereby critical reflection on one's assumptions leads to revised frames of reference and new ways of understanding one's role and capacity for action. The shifts reported by MOOC participants – particularly

their changed understanding of technology as an intrinsic dimension of democracy rather than merely a tool – are a clear example of this kind of perspective transformation.

All three groups also demonstrated an increased awareness and understanding of everyday democracy. Youth participants and educators reported impacts relating to the recognition of power dynamics and inequalities, the relationship between democracy and daily life, and the role of media and technology. Consortium members highlighted shifts in their understanding of youth perspectives on democracy which, in some cases, led to strategic reorientation in how they engage with young people. These findings align with Biesta's (2011) argument that democratic education must move beyond teaching *about* citizenship toward 'learning democracy': creating conditions in which democratic subjectivity can emerge – conditions that require relational trust, critical dialogue, and space for disagreement.

Furthermore, partners and educators reported a significant strengthening and expansion of networks and collaborative opportunities, ranging from the institutional to the European level. All ten consortium members reported that the project generated potential for future collaboration, with five already having specific projects in preparation. This network-building represents an important dimension of second-order change, as it creates the relational infrastructure necessary for sustaining and scaling democratic education practices beyond the life of any single project.

Several challenges were identified that may inhibit the realisation of second-order impacts. The need for participants to have a prior critical understanding of democracy before engaging in debate was highlighted as important for avoiding unproductive conflict. Better structuring of reflective and futures-oriented activities was also identified as necessary for maximising engagement. The difficulty of maintaining engagement beyond programme sessions, and the potential for deeper outcomes if it were possible to work with one group over the whole programme rather than multiple groups, also emerged as important considerations. These challenges reflect the characteristic focus of second-order change on *how* work is being done and the pre-existing systems and structures that may enable or inhibit positive impacts.

4.2.3 Impacts as democracy (third-order change)

The CCLAB project's primary objectives centred on the development and validation of a scalable pedagogical model, with expected impacts oriented principally toward first- and second-order change. Third-order change was not an explicit objective of the project. Nevertheless, the evaluation data reveal indications that the project's activities did, in some

cases, catalyse deeper shifts in participants' beliefs, values and assumptions. Ideally, the accumulation of positive impacts at the first- and second-order change levels can stimulate the emergence of the more transformative type of impacts and changes that characterise third-order change, where there is some form of deeper examination and surfacing of underlying and often unconscious barriers to genuine transformation. There are indications that the CCLAB project has indeed managed to generate several impacts as democracy – that is, impacts that involve fundamental shifts in the beliefs, values, and assumptions of participants, opening up possibilities for genuinely systemic transformation.

For youth participants, the critical thinking, communication, and collaboration skills acquired through the PAR cycles, mentorships, and Youth Advisory Board boosted their self-confidence and sense of agency, which then translated into direct action in their schools and communities. This trajectory from awareness to agency to action reflects an emerging movement through the levels of citizenship described by Westheimer and Kahne (2004), from personally responsible to participatory and, in some cases, towards justice-oriented citizenship. The third level of this model describes citizens who go beyond volunteering or participating in civic action, to critically assess structural conditions and pursue change that addresses the root causes of injustice. Two of the four youth interviewees moved from purely online engagement to joining local organisations, engaging in climate activism, while another youth participant was reported by a consortium member to have become involved in European Parliament youth initiatives following their participation in a CCLAB. These examples suggest that for some participants, the CCLAB experience acted as a catalyst for the kind of participatory and justice-oriented action that Westheimer and Kahne (2004) describe.

For educators, project participation increased motivation to connect their classrooms with the wider community and shifted their beliefs about how they can support students to take meaningful action. The perspective shifts reported by MOOC participants – such as reconceptualising technology as constitutive of democratic life rather than merely instrumental to it – represent what Mezirow (1997) terms a transformation of *habits of mind*: deep-seated, often taken-for-granted assumptions that shape how individuals interpret and engage with the world. Such shifts are qualitatively different from the acquisition of new skills or knowledge; they alter the interpretive framework within which all subsequent learning and action takes place.

Consortium members also benefitted from shifts in perception that motivated strategic review and restructuring of how they will engage with young people on democracy-related activities in the future. Several consortium members reported that the project opened up

opportunities for them to expand their work on democratic education and to engage with additional youth audiences. One consortium member's city council has decided to fund an extension of the CCLAB and PAR cycles for 15–18-year olds living in student accommodation in the city and to further expand this nationally in the coming years. This represents an institutional commitment to sustaining third-order change beyond the project's lifespan.

A significant enabling factor for third-order change was the three-year duration of the CCLAB project, which was felt to be instrumental in achieving the depth of outcomes observed. Partners consistently highlighted how the iterative PAR cycle structure – with built-in time for reflection, revision, and re-engagement – allowed for a quality and depth of learning that shorter projects cannot support. This finding aligns with Mezirow's (1997) emphasis on the role of critical reflection over time in enabling perspective transformation, and with Sterling's (2011) argument that third-order change in education requires sustained engagement that allows people to examine their worldview from the outside, rather than seeing through it, creating space for alternative perspectives and possibilities.

However, it is important to be candid about the limits of what was achieved at this third-order level. While the impacts described above represent meaningful shifts in individual beliefs, values, and orientations, they remain largely at the level of individual or small-group transformation. There is less evidence from the evaluation data that the project achieved systemic or institutional third-order change – that is, a fundamental restructuring of the conditions, assumptions, and power relations within the educational institutions and systems in which the CCLAB operated. The perspective shifts reported by individual youth participants, educators, and consortium members are significant and should not be understated, but they sit within structures that have themselves remained largely unchanged.

This is not surprising when considered in light of the project's objectives and design. The CCLAB project's central objective was the development and validation of a scalable pedagogical model of democratic education that could be adapted and applied across diverse European contexts in the service of strengthening youth understanding of and participation in everyday democracy. This was an ambitious and valuable goal, and the model that has been produced (Durall et al., 2026) represents a genuine contribution to the field. However, a pedagogical model designed for transferability across contexts necessarily operates at a different level from the kind of deep, context-specific institutional change that third-order transformation typically involves. Achieving systemic change within educational institutions – restructuring power relations, surfacing taken-for-granted assumptions, reconfiguring decision-making processes – would require a different interventional logic:

one oriented toward organisational transformation within specific institutional settings, involving different stakeholders and sustained local engagement over time. This was not the CCLAB project's remit, nor would it have been compatible with the demands of a multi-partner, multi-country project operating across ten diverse institutional contexts.

What CCLAB has demonstrated is that a well-designed pedagogical model, supported by sufficient duration, iterative design and relational trust, can catalyse the individual and organisational perspective shifts from which systemic change may subsequently emerge. The challenge going forward is to consider how the model might be complemented by more intensive, locally embedded approaches in specific contexts where the conditions for deeper institutional transformation are favourable. This is explored further in Section 4.4 below.

Furthermore, as the literature on third-order change emphasises, ongoing commitment and effort is required to sustain impacts at this level, particularly in the face of resistance (Krawczyk et al., 2025). Challenges reported by participants are instructive in this regard. Some educators faced resistance and a lack of enthusiasm from institutional staff or families, as well as obstacles in the form of rigid curricula and inflexible timetables, while others identified constraints such as a lack of available networks to enable students to translate their ideas and motivations into tangible actions. Rather than representing shortcomings of the CCLAB project, whose objectives centred on strengthening democratic education rather than transforming educational institutions, these tensions point to a significant finding: that meaningful democracy education may ultimately require a rethinking of the structures and logics of the education systems in which they operate. Schools do not always operate in ways that are experienced as democratic by students, and this creates friction when participatory, justice-oriented pedagogies are introduced within them. This finding has implications for policy and curriculum design that extend beyond the scope of the CCLAB project.

4.3 Conditions for Transformation: Enablers and Barriers

Drawing together the findings across all three stakeholder groups, a number of cross-cutting conditions can be identified that either enabled or constrained the depth of transformative change achieved by the CCLAB project. Understanding these conditions is important for informing decisions about how best to sustain, scale, and institutionalise the CCLAB model's approach to democratic education.

4.3.1 Enablers

Duration and iterative design. The three-year project duration and the iterative PAR cycle structure emerged consistently as key enablers of deeper impact. Consortium members highlighted how the opportunity for reflection, revision, and re-engagement across cycles allowed for a quality of learning that shorter projects cannot support. This aligns with research on transformative learning that emphasises the importance of sustained, reflective engagement over time for genuine perspective shifts to occur (Mezirow, 1997; Sterling, 2011).

Creative and participatory methods. The use of creative, hands-on, and participatory activities, including making, theatre, personal sharing, and futures thinking (cf. D2.3: Laflin et al., 2026) was consistently identified as a strength of the CCLAB approach. These methods supported deeper engagement than theoretical approaches to citizenship education, and allowed participants to express values and concerns that more conventional approaches may not surface. The role of creative and embodied approaches in democratic education is well-established in the literature (Lee et al., 2020; Morgan, 2018) and resonates with Freire's (1970) emphasis on dialogue and praxis as foundations of critical consciousness.

Relational trust and emotional safety. The quality of relationships between facilitators and participants, and among participants themselves, was an important enabling factor across CCLAB contexts. Youth participants valued mentorship relationships, while consortium members highlighted the importance of open and ongoing communication with young people. The CCLAB deliverable D3.4 (Del Razo Martínez et al., 2026) identifies relational infrastructures – including trust-based relationships, emotional safety, and pedagogical adaptability – as critical to sustaining participatory initiatives, a finding strongly reinforced by this impact evaluation.

Cross-European collaboration and network-building. The consortium structure provided opportunities for cross-national and cross-disciplinary learning that enriched all consortium members' work. The value of connecting with partners across Europe, sharing expertise, and gaining both comparative and disciplinary perspectives was widely reported within the consortium members. These networks represent a form of social capital that has ongoing value beyond the project's lifespan, creating conditions for continued collaboration, mutual learning, and joint policy influence.

4.3.2 Barriers

Structural rigidities and institutional resistance in formal education. Pre-existing classroom dynamics, rigid curricula, inflexible timetables, were identified as significant barriers to innovation in democracy education that the CCLAB project strives towards. Together with other factors such as resistance within educational institutions and the wider community, such structural conditions constrain the depth and continuity of engagement possible within formal education settings and represent a fundamental tension for projects aspiring to transformational change within existing institutional frameworks.

Time, space, and resource constraints. Time limitations were the most frequently cited challenge across all groups. For youth, competing commitments and holiday periods affected attendance. For educators, insufficient time to integrate new approaches into already full curricula was a persistent concern and constrained the potential to achieve lasting impact. For consortium members, the compressed nature of activities within some PAR cycles limited the depth of exploration possible on complex topics and the challenge of building trust, sustaining engagement in an era of distraction, and of translating awareness and motivation into consequential action was a common thread, reflecting a systemic undervaluation of the time required for genuine participatory processes (Cornwell, 2008). This is a well-recognised challenge in transformative education, as the depth of change sought requires extended engagement that does not always align with project-based or institutional timeframes (Sterling, 2011). The companion CCLAB deliverable on process evaluation (D3.1 Malinverni et al., 2025) goes further, arguing that compressed timeframes and a productivist logic of rapid results can actively suspend rather than enable agency, exhausting participants' capacity for the kind of reflective, imaginative work that third-order change requires.

Gaps in professional development and support. Educators identified a need for ongoing professional development, open-access resources, and community networks for implementation support. This echoes the 2022 EU Council Recommendation on learning for the green transition and sustainable development, which emphasises the need for targeted support, expertise, and training opportunities for educators seeking to integrate transformative approaches into their practice (Council of the European Union, 2022) – a policy direction that applies equally to democratic education.

4.4 Limitations of this study

A number of limitations should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings of this impact evaluation. These relate to the scope and nature of the data collected, the constraints under which data collection took place, and the methodological implications of these for the conclusions drawn.

The most significant concerns the youth data. The Grant Agreement envisaged ten youth interviews; four were conducted, reflecting lower-than-anticipated uptake of the MYCELIA mentoring programme and the practical challenges of conducting in-depth qualitative interviews across a multilingual, multi-country project. The youth impact findings are therefore drawn from a smaller and more heterogeneous evidence base than intended, comprising four interviews and a mixed sample of focus group records and reflective essays from the PAR cycle evaluation. With a dataset of this composition, it is not possible to claim data saturation. The findings should be read as illustrative of the kinds of impact the project generated rather than as comprehensive or generalisable. To mitigate this, the analysis drew on supplementary data from PAR cycle evaluation records across all project locations. This included direct testimony from youth reflective essays, as well as extracts from summaries of focus groups with youth, and diaries in which researchers and educators had reported on observed youth impacts. Together, these sources provide a broader perspective, though the reliance in the latter case on adult observations as a complement to direct youth voice is itself a limitation, and one that sits in some tension with the project's commitment to centring youth perspectives.

More broadly, the evaluation design reflects how youth impact assessment was distributed across the project's work packages. The primary youth engagement in the CCLAB project took place through the PAR cycles, involving over 2,100 young people, and the impacts on these activities were evaluated extensively as part of the process evaluation (D3.1: Malinverni et al., 2026). The impact evaluation task (T3.2) was designed to draw its youth evidence from the MYCELIA mentoring programme (and later extended to include the Youth Advisory Board), activities that, while valuable, engaged a smaller number of participants in a different mode of involvement. As a result, the most substantial body of youth data, that gathered through the PAR cycles and analysed in D3.1 (Malinverni et al., 2026), is primarily oriented toward process evaluation and model refinement, while the impact evaluation (D3.3) draws on a more focused set of youth experiences. Readers seeking a comprehensive picture of the project's effects on youth participants are therefore encouraged to consider the findings in this report alongside the report D3.1 (Malinverni et al., 2026).

The educator survey data (n=169) fell modestly short of the 200 responses anticipated in the task description but remains robust for the purposes of this evaluation. As with all self-report instruments, the surveys capture confidence and intentions rather than observed changes in practice, and without longitudinal follow-up it is not possible to determine whether reported intentions translate into sustained behavioural change. Some degree of positive response bias is also likely, as respondents who completed the surveys may represent a more engaged subset of participants.

The consortium member data is the most complete dataset, with all ten partner organisations represented. However, as organisational stakeholders with an interest in the project's success, interviewees may have been inclined toward positive reporting. The analysis sought to address this by attending to challenges and tensions alongside positive impacts.

Across the project, lower-than-anticipated recruitment to programmes and trainings reflect structural realities in education systems, as educators increasingly report operating under significant curriculum pressures and time poverty (Creagh et al., 2023), while young people face competing demands on their time alongside the practical barriers of multilingual research participation. These constraints are themselves symptomatic of the broader systemic barriers to participatory and democratic education that the CCLAB project seeks to address.

It is also important to situate the project and its evaluation within the wider context in which it took place. The CCLAB project ran from 2023 to 2026 – a period of significant global geopolitical instability, and a rapidly shifting European political landscape. While the project's original risk assessment anticipated some of these dynamics, the pace and intensity of change during this period exceeded what could reasonably have been foreseen at design stage. The rapid mainstreaming of generative AI, continued concerns about social media's effects on youth wellbeing, and evolving debates about digital sovereignty and platform regulation substantially altered the technology and media environments within which young people and educators operate. These dynamics are not merely background context; they actively shaped the conditions under which the project operated, the issues that participants brought to the CCLABs, and the challenges faced in sustaining engagement and institutional support. It is therefore worth noting that the landscape in which the project's impacts will unfold continues to evolve in ways that are difficult to predict.

More broadly, the impact evaluation captures impacts at a single point in time, relatively close to the end of the project. Many of the impacts described, particularly those

categorised as second- and third-order change in Section 4.2, are by their nature emergent and evolving. Their durability and depth will only become fully apparent over a longer timeframe than this evaluation permits.

It should also be acknowledged that impacts of this kind are difficult to attribute to any single intervention. Participants' development during the project period will have been influenced by many other factors alongside their involvement in CCLAB. The findings should therefore be understood as evidence that CCLAB contributed to the impacts described, rather than as claims of causation.

Finally, this deliverable does not offer a description of the individual Critical ChangeLabs that took place across Europe, as these are detailed in other CCLAB project deliverables (D2.1 & D2.2: Laflin et al., 2025a; Laflin et al., 2025b) and in the comprehensive process evaluation (D3.1: Malinverni et al., 2026). The present report focuses on impact at the aggregate level, which means that important contextual variation between countries, settings, and participant groups is not fully captured here. Readers interested in the process-level detail and context-specific findings are directed to the companion deliverables mentioned above, available on the CCLAB project community space on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/cclab/records>.

5. Conclusions & Recommendations

This final chapter draws together the findings of the impact evaluation to offer a set of recommendations for policy and practice, and to reflect on the conditions under which the CCLAB model's approach to democratic education can be sustained and developed beyond the project's lifespan. The recommendations presented here are informed by and complement the practitioner-oriented recommendations in the process evaluation (Chapter 9 of D3.1: Malinverni et al., 2026) and the policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy (D4.6: Milanese et al., 2025). Readers are directed to those companion deliverables for fuller detail on specific pedagogical and policy dimensions.

5.1 Overview of Key Findings

The impact evaluation demonstrates that the Critical ChangeLab project generated a substantial body of positive impacts across the three stakeholder groups examined – youth participants, educators, and consortium members – with consistent patterns of impact visible across all three. Applying the Three Orders of Change framework (Bartunek & Moch, 1987), adapted for the democratic education context, reveals that the project achieved impacts at all three levels: impacts *about* democracy (first-order), through the creation of novel resources, content, and organisational capacity; impacts *for* democracy (second-order), through skills development, expanded awareness of everyday democracy, strengthened networks, and enhanced confidence among all groups; and emerging impacts *as* democracy (third-order), through shifts in beliefs, values, and assumptions that open up possibilities for more fundamental transformation – in the words of Gert Biesta "from teaching citizenship to learning democracy" (2011, p. 5).

The most transformative impacts were associated with several key enabling conditions: the three-year project duration and iterative PAR cycle structure, which allowed for sustained reflection and revision; the use of creative, participatory, and imaginative methods that engaged participants beyond conventional pedagogical formats; the quality of relational trust between facilitators and participants; and the grounding of programme content in issues of direct relevance to young people's lived experience. Where these conditions were present, the project was able to catalyse genuine shifts in agency, critical awareness, and civic action – particularly among youth participants, several of whom moved from passive engagement to active involvement in local and European-level democratic initiatives.

At the same time, the evaluation identified significant structural barriers that constrained the depth of transformation possible, particularly in formal education settings. Rigid curricula, inflexible timetables, institutional resistance, and pre-existing authority dynamics limited what could be achieved within the time and space available. The project's design priority of developing a scalable pedagogical model – while producing a genuine and valuable contribution to the field – also meant that the kind of deep, context-specific institutional analysis required for systemic third-order change was not the primary focus. The third-order impacts that were achieved remained concentrated at the level of individual and organisational perspective shifts rather than extending to structural transformation of the educational systems themselves.

These findings point to a clear conclusion: the CCLAB model has demonstrated its capacity to generate meaningful and, in some cases, transformative impacts on youth, educators, and organisations engaged in democratic education. The challenge going forward is to create the structural, institutional, and policy conditions that would allow these impacts to deepen, scale, and endure.

5.2 Recommendations for Policy and Practice

Drawing on the preceding analysis, this section provides a suite of recommendations aimed at policymakers at EU, national, and local levels; educational institutions and organisations; and educators and practitioners.

5.2.1 For policymakers (EU, national, and local)

- **Recognise democratic education as a core institutional responsibility**, supported by dedicated curriculum time, sustainable resources, and systemic incentives – not as an add-on or time-limited project initiative.
- **Design funding models that support sustained, iterative engagement.** Short-term interventions are insufficient for deeper change; compressed timeframes can actively work against the development of agency and imagination.
- **Invest in educator professional development for democracy education**, including decentralised training platforms, peer networks, and transdisciplinary teacher professional learning, so that democracy education is integrated across the curriculum.

- **Bridge formal and non-formal education settings** through community partnerships, structured collaborations, and curriculum frameworks that accommodate participatory approaches.
- **Embed participative democratic health assessment in institutional practice**, using tools such as the Democracy Health Questionnaire to support self-assessment and, potentially, to inform EU-level democratic monitoring, with continued development to strengthen the instrument's action-oriented dimensions (see Section 3.4 and Annex 2).

5.2.2 For educational institutions and organisations

- **Move from teaching about democracy to becoming sites of democracy**, creating genuine opportunities for students to exercise agency, engage in dialogue, and influence decisions that affect them.
- **Use the Democracy Health Questionnaire for participative self-assessment**, involving students and staff as a basis for ongoing reflection and improvement. Formative feedback gathered through focus groups (see Section 3.4 and Annex 2) indicates that the DHQ is valued as a reflective tool but would benefit from the development of stronger action-oriented components, enabling institutions to move from diagnosis to concrete planning for improvement.
- **Create conditions for sustained engagement** through flexible timetabling and external partnerships – prioritising depth over breadth of coverage.
- **Foster community partnerships and external collaboration** as a systemic function, not a project-based add-on.

5.2.3 For educators and practitioners

- **Adopt co-creative, youth-centred approaches**, starting from young people's own concerns and building outward. The CCLAB Educator's Handbook "Democracy in the Making: Creative Methods for Youth & Educators" (Laflin et al., 2026), the CCLAB MOOC² and the Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy (Durall et al., 2026) provide practical guidance.

² <https://digicampus.fi/course/view.php?id=5919>

- **Develop relational skills as core professional competencies.** Trust, emotional safety, mentorship, and pedagogical adaptability are constitutive of democratic education, not peripheral to it.
- **Cultivate imagination as a core competency,** using creative, artistic, transdisciplinary and futures-oriented methods.

5.3 Looking Forward

The Critical ChangeLab project has produced a tested, flexible, and scalable model of democratic pedagogy, supported by a substantial suite of resources – including an Educator’s Handbook, a MOOC, a Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index, and evidence-based policy recommendations – that are freely available for use by educators, institutions, researchers, and policymakers. This evaluation demonstrates that the model is capable of generating meaningful impacts at multiple levels, including, under favourable conditions, the kind of transformative shifts in perspective and agency that represent genuine third-order change.

Moving beyond individual and organisational perspective shifts toward systemic structural change would require complementary approaches: more intensive, locally or nationally embedded interventions sustained over longer timeframes than any single funded project can typically provide. The CCLAB model has demonstrated that it can catalyse the conditions from which such transformation may emerge; the question beyond the lifetime of the project is whether the structural and policy environment will support it.

There are grounds for cautious optimism. All consortium members reported that the project has generated potential for future collaboration, with five already having specific projects in preparation. One consortium member’s city council has committed to funding an extension of the CCLAB. The MOOC and Educator’s Handbook are available as open resources for a growing community of practice. Several consortium members have embedded project methods and approaches into their existing teacher education programmes, research agendas, and organisational strategies. These are not merely project outputs; they represent an emerging infrastructure for the continued development and dissemination of democratic pedagogy across Europe.

The current European policy context, while challenging, also presents significant opportunities. The European Commission’s Democracy Shield initiative (European Commission & High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, 2025), the development of the Union of Skills (European Commission, 2025), and the Council of

Europe's Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (Council of Europe, 2018) all create entry points for the kind of comprehensive democracy education that the CCLAB project advocates. As D4.6 (Del Razo Martínez et al., 2026) argues, the concepts of everyday democracy, critical consciousness, participative democratic health, and creative technological environments that underpin the CCLAB model offer a substantive and evidence-based contribution to these policy agendas – one that goes beyond defensive responses to specific threats toward a positive vision of democratic education as the foundation of resilient European societies.

The CCLAB project began from the conviction that democracy is not only something to be taught about but something to be lived and practised. The impact evaluation confirms that when young people, educators, and organisations are given the time, space, methods, and relational support to engage in this practice together, meaningful change is possible. The task now is to ensure that these conditions are not the exception but the norm – embedded in curricula, supported by policy, and sustained by the kinds of collaborative networks and institutional commitments that this project has helped to build.

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Annex 1

Research Instruments

Interview Protocol for Youth: MYCELIA Programme

Theme	Question	Further prompts
General Intro	Overall, can you describe your mentorship experience? What was the focus of the mentorship?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Was this your first time working with a wider European project/organisation? What were your expectations at the beginning? Did they change over time? What parts of the experience felt most meaningful or surprising to you? Did the mentoring relationship help you reflect on your own abilities, choices, or possible futures *(linked to developing transformative agency)*?
Everyday Democracy	Did your mentoring experience change the way you think about democracy, participation, or how people can make change in everyday life? Can you give an example?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Did you notice any differences in how you listened to or engaged with others after starting the programme? Did you discuss everyday issues (e.g., fairness, inclusion, respect) and connect them to broader democratic ideas? Do you feel you now better understand how democracy shows up in daily actions (“everyday democracy”) and how your own behaviour contributes to it?
Power Dynamics & Awareness of Inequality	Through your role as a mentor or mentee, did you become more aware of inequalities, power dynamics, or injustices around you online, at school, or in your community? How did the programme help you	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Did conversations with your mentor/mentee help you notice any unfairness or inequalities you hadn't thought about before? Did the programme help you think about whose voices are heard or not heard in certain situations (a key part of democratic participation)?

	respond to or act on these issues?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did the programme help you imagine ways—even small ones—in which you could respond to or challenge something you saw as unjust?
Sustainability & Taking Action	Since being part of MYCELIA, have you taken any actions, big or small—towards solving an issue that bothers you or improving something in your environment or address an issue you care about? What gave you the confidence or motivation to do this?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did mentoring help you plan, imagine, or test out possible actions (linked to building transformative agency)? • Did your mentor/mentee help you see possible pathways to change or help you reflect on next steps? • Did you collaborate with others—friends, classmates, community members—on anything connected to what you discussed during mentoring? • Even small changes count— have your habits, attitudes, confidence, or sense of responsibility changed as a result of the programme? • Do you feel more capable of making decisions, solving problems, or influencing your surroundings?
Personal development & skills	What skills or personal strengths do you feel have developed through MYCELIA?	
Concluding	What do you think the biggest impact that taking part in the MYCELIA programme has had in your own life?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did it affect your sense of agency— your belief that you can create change? • If you could share one message with policymakers or educators about why programmes like MYCELIA matter for young people, what would it be?

Interview Protocol for Consortium Members

Introduction to interview:

Thanks for agreeing to talk to us today for the impact evaluation report. Our goal for these meetings is to have short meetings with partners to talk about the impact that

CCLAB has had. We understand ‘impact’ to be anything that exists as a result of the CCLAB that wasn’t there before, or wouldn’t exist without it.

We are conducting surveys, interviews with youth, and looking at our interviews with educators to better understand our impact in those spaces, but for the next 20 mins or so we want to focus on what impact the project has had on the partner organisations themselves. We want you to answer (as best as you can) for the organisation you represent. We want to capture our stories and anecdotes for the final report. The responses you give today will inform Partner Impact Stories in the impact evaluation. We have five questions in total, and only about 20 mins, so it will be a short interview that will be more of a conversation.

Questions asked for interview:

Impact of organisation	Question
General impact	Looking back, what difference has CCLAB made in your organisation (if any)?
Impact on initiatives and project	Has your experience with CCLAB influenced other projects, research, or initiatives you’re involved in?
Impact on approaches to engagement	Did CCLAB change anything in how you or your colleagues approach teaching, facilitation, or working with young people?
Impact on networks and relationships	Did CCLAB create or strengthen any important relationships or networks for you?

Impact on young people	If you had to tell one short story that captures the impact of CCLAB on young people in your context, what would you choose?
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Survey for Educators (Training) and Educators (PAR)

A. Consent

1. Consent to Participate

Participant's Agreement: I, the participant, agree to my survey responses and data being stored on Trinity College Dublin's secure drive for use by the Critical ChangeLab project to evaluate the impact of the project. Further details can be found on the privacy notice*

Yes No

B. Initial reflections: Confidence and pedagogical understanding

2. How confident do you feel in supporting youth to engage with democracy in everyday contexts after this training?

Response scale: 1 = Not at all confident | 5 = Very confident

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Overall confidence	<input type="checkbox"/>				

3. To what extent do you agree with the following statements: After this training)? (Rate 1-5)

Response scale: 1 = Totally disagree | 5 = Totally agree

Item	1	2	3	4	5
I understand how to integrate democratic	<input type="checkbox"/>				

pedagogy in my teaching.

I can design learning activities that help youth recognise their ability to shape their futures and make a difference, changing things for the better.

I see everyday democracy as relevant to classroom practice.

4. What part of this training event was most meaningful or useful to you?

C. Expected implementation

5. How likely are you to implement the following aspects of a Critical ChangeLab in your future practice?

Response scale: 1 = Very unlikely | 5 = Very likely

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Participatory action research with students	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Collaborative projects involving external	<input type="checkbox"/>				

community stakeholders						
Creative methods to explore democratic ideas	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The critical literacies framework	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Imagining alternative futures with students	<input type="checkbox"/>					

6. What challenges do you anticipate in applying these approaches in your teaching context?

7. What kind of support or resources would help you implement these methods?

E. Youth Agency: Supporting democratic learning outcomes

8. After this training, how confident do you feel in supporting students to:

Response scale: 1 = Not at all confident | 5 = Very confident

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Understand democracy as a way of living and interacting with others - based on respect, inclusion, and shared responsibility.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Plan and take meaningful action in their local communities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Engage critically with digital platforms as citizens.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

F. Reflection and future use

9. Have you experienced any personal shift in how you view education and democracy from this training?

10. Do you intend to run a Critical ChangeLab in your own classroom with students?

- Yes No Not sure

11. If yes, how?

12. If no, why not? Are there barriers to implementing this in your practice?

13. How likely are you to recommend this training to others in teacher education?

Response scale: 1 = Not likely | 5 = Extremely likely

Item	1	2	3	4	5
Likelihood to recommend	<input type="checkbox"/>				

14. Why or why not?

G. Participant background

15. Type of learning environment you do / you expect to work in:

- Formal education (Primary / Secondary / Vocational / Higher Education)
- Non-formal education / Informal learning environments
- Technology Development
- Youth Work

Other: _____

16. Country of training:

17. (Optional) Please share any other reflections or comments you may have about the training or the Critical ChangeLab model:

Survey for Educators (MOOC, administered via DigiCampus)

Section 1. Confidence and self-assessment

1. How confident do you feel in applying ideas and approaches from this course in your own practice?

Please rate on a 1-5 scale. (1 = Not at all confident – 5 = Very confident)

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Overall confidence in applying ideas and approaches from the course	<input type="checkbox"/>				

2. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Please rate each statement from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
I understand how technology and democracy intersect in today's world.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I can assess in what way democratic engagement is relevant to my work or practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I can design activities that help youth critically engage with social and technological issues.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section 2. Most meaningful course elements

3. What part of the course was most meaningful or useful to you?

Select all that apply.

<input type="checkbox"/> Critically reflecting on the relationship between technology and democracy	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning about new activities and methods
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<input type="checkbox"/> Discovering new case studies	<input type="checkbox"/> Connecting the module content with my own work or practice
<input type="checkbox"/> A specific module	<input type="checkbox"/> Other

Section 3. Expected Implementation

4. How likely are you to integrate the following into your future work and/or practice?

Please rate each item from 1 (very unlikely) to 5 (very likely).

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Creative or arts-based methods to explore democratic and social ideas	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Activities that encourage imagining alternative futures	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Approaches to developing critical literacies or critical consciousness	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Participatory activities involving young people	<input type="checkbox"/>				

and community stakeholders					
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Section 4. Anticipated challenges and supports

5. What challenges do you anticipate in applying these approaches?

Select all that apply.

- Time, space or resources (e.g. access to technology, inflexible timetables, unsuitable rooms, limited access to materials)
- Institutional or policy barriers (e.g. staff/family resistance, rigid curricula, lack of enthusiasm from leadership)
- Capacity or support (e.g. gaps in your own professional development, uncertainty about facilitating controversial topics)
- Lack of potential for student agency (e.g. student proposals are not implemented, lack of networks to transform ideas into action)
- Other

6. What kind of support or resources would help you implement the methods?

Select all that apply.

- Materials (e.g. open-access resources, lesson plans, teaching guides, or activity sheets)
- Institutional support (e.g. commitment to spending class time on the topic, job security for facilitators, integration with institutional policy)
- Professional development (e.g. opportunities to engage in ongoing training for the educator)
- Community network (e.g. for implementing projects in the wider community, mentorship)
- Other

Section 5. Preparedness after the MOOC

7. After this MOOC, I feel prepared to support young people to:

Please rate each statement from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Recognise the relationship between technology in everyday life and democracy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Understand democracy as a way of living and interacting with others—based on respect, inclusion, and shared responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Engage critically with digital platforms and technologies as citizens	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Become more active citizens	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section 6. Reflection

8. Have you experienced any personal shift in how you view the relationship between youth, democracy, and technology as a result of this course? If so, how?

9. How likely are you to recommend this course to others?

Please rate on a 1-5 scale.

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Recommendation likelihood	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Annex 2

Analysis of focus group on Democracy Health Questionnaire

Authors: Lorelaj Lukačin & Boris Jokić

The Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ) is a self-assessment tool designed for both formal and non-formal education institutions to evaluate their level of democratic culture and plan future improvements. It was developed as part of CCLAB WPI (MAP & DESIGN), Task 1.1. It is primarily intended for institutional leaders but is recommended to be completed collaboratively to ensure diverse perspectives and foster participation in institutional development. Two comparable versions of the DHQ were developed, one for schools and one for institutions and organisations that offer non-formal education programmes. Both versions are aligned in their conceptual framework while accounting for contextual differences. The questionnaire is based on two broad areas that encompass institutions' democracy health: democratic values (*participation, accountability and transparency, equality, diversity, and inclusion and eco-social responsibility*) and democratic practices, which are understood as mutually reinforcing. Democratic practices and values are assessed across key stages of the educational programme cycle (*development, access, delivery, outcomes and impact*). In line with its self-assessment purpose, respondents provide a percentage-based response for each value and practice along three dimensions: *perceived importance, current level, and expected level in five years*.

Focus Groups

To assess participants' experiences of completing the questionnaire and identify potential issues in item clarity and comprehension as well as to gather feedback on its structure, three focus groups were conducted. Additionally, the focus groups aimed to collect suggestions for improving the DHQ in order to enhance its clarity, relevance, and future dissemination. Focus groups were conducted by Tactical Tech, one of the members of the CCLAB project consortium. Each focus group comprised 3-7 participants (14 participants in total) who were heads of formal or non-formal educational institutions, or individuals in charge of educational services in relevant institutions. They hailed from seven different countries: Germany, Romania, Portugal, Italy, Kenya, England, and Ivory Coast. The focus groups were conducted online, via video meeting platform. Before attending the focus group, each participant completed the DHQ, either formal or non-formal version, depending on the profile of their institution. The participants were also instructed to take notes of any insights, reflections or needs for clarification while completing the DHQ.

Experience of completing the DHQ

Overall, participants described the experience of completing the DHQ as intuitive, easy to use, and well-structured. The questionnaire was generally perceived as clear and accessible, with several participants highlighting its practical value and its potential to stimulate reflection on institutional practices:

“That was the good thing that I find in this questionnaire. That it can work as a tool and it is definitely very practical to help educators to reach the goals.”

“I said it was a bit unusual for me. It had some questions that made me think about the work, the things we are doing as an organization which given that we are young as an organisation... we haven't had really get any chance to ask ourselves those questions. I would say it was a surprising of it, but it got me thinking, so, I guess it was good.”

For some, the questionnaire was described as thought-provoking as it encouraged reflection on aspects of organisational work that are not typically discussed, particularly in relation to long-term planning and democratic culture:

“In my experience, with my organisation, is that we mainly talk about one year, or maybe the next two years, but not very often about the next five years... So, so that was a good experience and a good input to think about the long term”.

Despite these positive impressions, several challenges were identified. A recurring theme concerned the difficulty of responding from an appropriate perspective. Participants expressed uncertainty about whether they should answer from a personal, programme-level, or whole-organisation perspective, particularly in large or complex institutions:

“So, sometimes it's difficult to reply to the question regarding programme for the current state of the art or the expectation because I don't understand if it's from my point of view or from the organisation, the whole organisation point of view, from my single unit or working group.”

This ambiguity was especially pronounced when questions required estimations at the organisational level, which some participants felt exceeded their scope of knowledge or responsibility:

“It was hard to speak for the organisation when, I imagine, you are responsible for a specific program. And then, you've been asked questions for the overall organisation.”

"For me, it was really hard because, as I described, we are such a huge house, with so many departments to like concentrate in one department."

"... It was more suitable for, let's say, for my headmaster, the directors of the school, maybe."

Relatedly, participants emphasised that the questionnaire may be difficult to complete accurately by a single individual. Several suggested that a more reliable assessment would require input from multiple stakeholders, ideally including individuals in decision-making positions, in order to capture diverse perspectives and ensure informed responses.

"I think it's difficult for only one person to complete to fill in the questionnaire. Now that I'm thinking like that, even for headmaster, I think is difficult. Maybe he or she would need a small team to see all the perspectives. "

Another important issue concerned the use of percentage-based response scales. While participants generally found the interface easy to use, estimating percentages was perceived somewhat subjective. Some participants indicated a preference for more familiar Likert-type scales, noting that distinguishing between, for example, 60% and 70% was not always intuitive.

"There was no difficulty in understanding the task. However, I do agree with [other respondent] on the idea of answering in percentages, that might have been a bit difficult even though the whole dragging and everything in terms of functionality, that easy to use, and there's no problem with three parts. The percentages made me think, what makes 70% better than 60%, okay? "

Participants also highlighted a lack of clarity regarding the purpose of the questionnaire. While some understood it as a tool for reflecting on democratic practices within their institution, others reported uncertainty about how the data would be used. In addition, participants suggested that providing an estimated completion time at the beginning of the questionnaire would improve the user experience:

"I think it'd be useful to have a briefing information sheet on the homepage of the questionnaire explaining why this questionnaire is designed and what it aims to achieve. "

"...it would have been nice to know up-front how long it takes so I could plan better. "

Also, one participant pointed out that it was a "moral questionnaire" and could provoke socially desirable answers ("So felt the urge to always pick a high number because it was so obviously the right thing to do. ").

The overall structure of the questionnaire, particularly the division into importance, current state, and expectations for the future, was largely perceived as meaningful and appropriate. Participants appreciated the opportunity to differentiate between what is currently achievable and what is desirable, noting that this distinction facilitated deeper reflection on organisational goals and limitations.

"I think it was very good. I liked it because I think there's a big difference of what we as an organisation want and what we think is possible. And to get to reflect on this question and not only answering what this is now but what do we want it to be, but also, what we want to do."

However, some participants questioned whether the term "expectations" might be misleading, as responses in this category were sometimes based more on aspirations or ideal scenarios than on realistic projections.

"So, in that case, I was wondering that instead of saying expectations, so would that be more to do with aspiration rather than expectation?"

Regarding the internal organisation of the questionnaire, participants found the grouping of items according to phases of the educational programme (e.g., development, access, delivery, outcomes, and impact) to be logical and helpful for focusing their thinking. While some noted that real-life processes are not always linear, the structured grouping of related questions was perceived as beneficial for maintaining coherence and thematic focus during completion.

Nevertheless, some participants suggested that the questionnaire could benefit from additional flexibility or depth, for example by allowing more space for elaboration or by including elements that capture nuances not fully reflected in fixed response options.

"The survey is structured to give set of deliverables of the objective which makes it rigid. I suggest more details included to capture what is not captured by the available option to choose from."

Participants generally reported that the questionnaire items were clear and easy to understand. Most indicated that they did not encounter major difficulties in interpreting the questions, and several described them as accessible and straightforward.

Perceived relevance of the DHQ

Participants largely perceived the DHQ as a relevant and potentially valuable tool for their institutions. Many emphasised its importance in encouraging reflection on democratic

practices and values, particularly in contexts where such discussions are not commonly part of everyday organisational processes. The questionnaire was seen as especially useful for initiating internal dialogue and supporting self-evaluation efforts:

"I think for my organisation, it's very relevant because we don't ask ourselves these kind of questions very often in our usual day-to-day work. So, to have the time, this very relevant because I think all of the questions were relevant. "

"I think it would be a good start for schools to reflect towards the involvement in democratic projects with students. "

"I think most of the Portuguese schools have a self-evaluation team that works about self-evaluation of our school and different parts are also have a questionnaire that different students, teachers, parents answer... But I don't think our self-evaluation has this kind of questions."

At the same time, some participants expressed uncertainty regarding the practical application of the results, noting that reflection alone may not be sufficient to drive change without clear follow-up actions.

"I cannot imagine now how much I can we take from this work and take it to real projects. Right now, I can't imagine how practical it can be. It needs more focus and testing, for sure. "

"...it's nice to take a moment and reflect on our work, but also It's not like, what's the outcome for us other than reflection? I think only reflection doesn't change anything. "

Suggestions for improvement and future use

Participants provided a range of suggestions for improving the DHQ and enhancing its practical application. A key recommendation was to involve multiple stakeholders in the completion process, rather than relying on a single respondent. This approach was seen as more likely to produce a balanced and accurate assessment, particularly in complex institutions, and could include input from teachers, management, and, in adapted forms, students and other stakeholders, like parents.

"So, especially, young people, I mean using this questionnaire with them to ensure that the content we are proposing to them and the kind of training will give to them is a clear response to their needs. "

"I think it would be better if more people from the same school would complete the questionnaire."

"I'm thinking about parents, do you think they could answer somehow, The formal questionnaire, like, In some kind of, like, in a short version or something."

Although some participants highlight high frequency of questionnaires and surveys that are required from teachers to complete (*"I don't know this kind of It's appropriate for everybody because I think some teachers are tired of answering this kind of questionnaires."*).

In terms of content, participants proposed including additional elements that would enhance the practical value of the questionnaire. These included summaries of results, visual representations (e.g., profiles), and concrete recommendations based on responses. Such features were seen as important for moving beyond reflection towards actionable change.

Conclusion

In conclusion, findings from the three focus groups indicate that the Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ) is generally perceived as a clear, relevant, and practically valuable tool for assessing and reflecting on democratic values and practices within educational institutions. Participants particularly emphasised its potential to stimulate critical reflection and support long-term thinking about institutional development. At the same time, the analysis identified several areas for improvement. These include the need for clearer guidance regarding the perspective from which responses should be provided, refinement of response formats, particularly percentage-based scales, and increased clarity regarding the purpose and intended use of the questionnaire. Participants also highlighted the importance of involving multiple stakeholders in the assessment process to ensure a more comprehensive and balanced evaluation. Overall, the DHQ appears to represent a strong foundation for institutional self-assessment of democratic culture.